

WHO Guidelines for malaria

Background papers and other unpublished evidence considered in the development of recommendations

Prevention/Vaccine (Section 4.3)

Title

Malaria vaccines evidence report: considerations for a three-dose versus four-dose vaccination schedule in areas of perennial malaria transmission

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This report is a background document for the joint session of Strategic Advisory Group of Experts on Immunization (SAGE) and the Malaria Policy Advisory Group (MPAG) held on 24 September 2025. It is being made publicly available for transparency purposes and information, in accordance with the *WHO handbook for guideline development, 2nd edition* (2014).

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Background paper

Malaria vaccines evidence report: considerations for a three-dose versus four- dose vaccination schedule in areas of perennial malaria transmission

Developed by the SAGE/MPAG Working Group on Malaria Vaccines to support the joint session of the Strategic Advisory Group of Experts on Immunization (SAGE) and the Malaria Policy Advisory Group (MPAG)

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Abbreviations

CI	confidence interval
COVID-19	coronavirus disease
CrI	credible interval
DALY	disability-adjusted life year
DSMB	Data and Safety Monitoring Board
GDP	gross domestic product
GRADE	Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation
GSK	GlaxoSmithKline
HBR	home-based record
HPV	human papillomavirus
ICER	incremental cost-effectiveness ratio
IPTp	intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy
IPTsc	intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in school-aged children
IQR	interquartile range
IRS	indoor residual spraying
ITN	insecticide-treated net
MCV-1	first dose of measles-containing vaccine
MCV-2	second dose of measles-containing vaccine
MPAG	Malaria Policy Advisory Group
MVIP	Malaria Vaccine Implementation Programme
NITAG	national immunization technical advisory group
OR	odds ratio
PCV	pneumococcal conjugate vaccine
PDMC	post-discharge malaria chemoprevention
Penta-3	third dose of pentavalent vaccine (protects against diphtheria, tetanus, pertussis, hepatitis B, and <i>Haemophilus influenzae</i> type b)
<i>PfPR</i>	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> parasite rate
PMC	perennial malaria chemoprevention
SAGE	Strategic Advisory Group of Experts on Immunization
SMC	seasonal malaria chemoprevention
UNICEF	United Nations Children's Fund
WHO	World Health Organization

Executive summary

Background

Malaria remains one of the leading causes of childhood morbidity and mortality, with the highest burden among children under 5 years of age living in sub-Saharan Africa. Progress against malaria has stalled, with more cases and deaths reported in 2023 than in 2015. Increased use of proven malaria control interventions is necessary to reduce the malaria burden. WHO recommends that countries use subnational tailoring to implement malaria interventions, including malaria vaccines, using local data and contextual information to determine the most effective mix of interventions to achieve the best impact with available resources.

WHO recommends malaria vaccines (RTS,S/AS01 and R21/Matrix-M) for the prevention of *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria in children living in malaria-endemic areas, prioritizing areas of moderate and high transmission. The first three doses are given from around 5 months of age, a minimum four weeks apart, with a fourth dose given 6–18 months after the third dose to prolong protection; a fifth dose is recommended in areas where the risk of malaria remains high in children over 3 years of age. As of 1 September 2025, 22 countries have adopted malaria vaccines in their childhood immunization programmes: Three countries introduced RTS,S/AS01 in 2019 as part of the Malaria Vaccine Implementation Programme (MVIP), and additional introductions of both vaccines followed in 2024 and 2025. The growing cumulative annual target population is currently over 9 million children. Twenty countries have opted for an age-based delivery approach with a four-dose schedule, while one country has opted for a hybrid delivery approach (first 3 doses age-based and subsequent doses annually just before the high transmission season) with a five-dose schedule.

Topic introduction

All evidence shows that a four-dose malaria vaccine schedule has a higher impact than a three-dose schedule. Findings from the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial (2009–2014) suggested that after a three-dose series, a fourth dose given 18 months after the third dose was needed to maintain vaccine efficacy against severe malaria and to avoid rebound of severe malaria cases. Review of the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 clinical trial data showed that vaccine efficacy against severe malaria was lower in the three-dose group than in the four-dose group before the administration of the fourth dose – a likely chance finding. The observed difference in vaccine efficacy between the three- and four-dose groups prior to administration of the fourth vaccine dose brought into question the interpretation of the comparison of the findings between the group who had received the fourth dose and the group who had not.

Findings from subsequent studies of RTS,S/AS01 have shown durable protection in children who receive three or four vaccine doses. Results from seven years of follow-up at three of the 11 RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial sites showed that, over the seven years, there were fewer cases of clinical malaria among children randomized to receive three or four vaccine doses compared to the control group, and any rebound that occurred was time-limited. During 46 months of surveillance for the MVIP (2019–2023), substantial and statistically significant impact was shown against severe malaria and all-cause mortality, despite only 40% of children having received the fourth vaccine dose.

The Strategic Advisory Group of Experts on Immunization (SAGE) and Malaria Policy Advisory Group (MPAG) previously endorsed a stepwise approach to evidence review and WHO policy recommendations for malaria vaccines, emphasizing that initial recommendations could be updated as new data became available – particularly new findings on the value of the fourth dose. If the recently completed case–control study shows that a fourth dose provides little incremental impact over a safe and effective three-dose schedule, there may be some contexts in which three doses could be recommended as an alternative to four doses.

As part of its mandate, the SAGE/MPAG Working Group on Malaria Vaccines has considered the following policy questions:

- Is a three-dose malaria vaccine schedule safe and effective?
- In areas of perennial malaria transmission (including low transmission), should a three-dose malaria vaccine schedule be considered as an alternative to a four-dose schedule in some contexts?

The relevant evidence was reviewed to develop evidence-based SAGE recommendations on vaccine policy and guidance.

Case–control study results on three versus four doses

The case–control study (2021–2025) nested within the MVIP was designed specifically to assess the value of the fourth dose, the incremental benefit of four doses over three doses, and the occurrence of rebound of severe malaria cases if a child were to receive only three doses of RTS,S/AS01. The case–control study was conducted within the context of vaccine delivery through the routine childhood immunization programmes in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi, and leveraged the sentinel hospital and community-based mortality surveillance systems established by in-country research partners for the MVIP (2019–2023).

Results from the case–control study showed that the protection against severe malaria provided by the first three doses until the scheduled age for the fourth dose was 56% (95% confidence interval [CI]: 40–67%). From the age when the fourth dose was due, among children who did not receive the fourth dose, the effectiveness of three doses against severe malaria was 35% (95% CI: 15–50%). Among children who received the fourth dose, RTS,S/AS01 provided substantial added protection against severe malaria over that provided by three doses, with an incremental effectiveness of the fourth dose against severe malaria of 30% (95% CI: 9–45%).

There was no rebound effect observed in children who received three doses. In contrast, children had sustained protection beyond the age when the fourth dose was due.

Resource use

The supply of malaria vaccines is now sufficient to meet demand, and funding is the primary barrier to access. The cost of the malaria vaccine is currently higher (R21/Matrix-M US\$ 3.90 per dose; RTS,S/AS01 EUR 9.30 [approximately US\$ 10.00 in 2024] per dose) than that of other Gavi-supported vaccines with longer-standing funding and procurement mechanisms. The costs for both products are expected to decrease over the next five years (2026–2030) as larger volumes are procured – with commitments from both manufacturers to reduce prices by 2028. Gavi, the Vaccine Alliance, currently offers support to eligible countries for malaria vaccine implementation in geographical areas selected by the countries, representing no more than 85% of the total population of children living within a country’s moderate and high transmission areas. This implies that most countries are proceeding with a phased, subnational introduction in selected areas, introducing the malaria vaccine as part of a mix of malaria interventions. All countries contribute domestic resources for vaccine procurement per Gavi’s co-financing policy, with the lowest income countries paying US\$ 0.20 per dose and higher income groups contributing more. There is a risk that Gavi support will be further limited by the funding gap affecting the 2026–2030 strategy period.

Shifting from a four-dose to a three-dose schedule could, in theory, reduce vaccine procurement and delivery costs for the immunization programme by up to 25%. However, the actual savings are likely to be lower and will vary depending on drop-out rates and country context. These reduced vaccine programme costs must be weighed against the increased costs from a rise in clinical and severe malaria cases owing to a less effective three-dose schedule.

Modelled public health impact and cost-effectiveness estimates

Mathematical modelling by two independent research groups estimated that a four-dose RTS,S/AS01 vaccine schedule always has a higher impact than a three-dose schedule on uncomplicated malaria cases, malaria deaths and disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) averted across malaria transmission levels and seasonal settings. At a transmission intensity of 20% *Plasmodium falciparum* parasite rate (PfPR), the fourth dose is estimated to avert an additional 25–35% of malaria cases and malaria deaths compared to three doses alone. This modelled impact of the fourth dose is consistent with the findings observed in the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial and the MVIP case–control study. A three-dose schedule is also estimated to have positive public health impact in terms of uncomplicated malaria cases, malaria deaths and DALYs averted, although the impact will be lower than with four doses.

Modelling estimated similar cost effectiveness ranges for three-dose and four-dose RTS,S/AS01 schedules compared to no vaccination. The models differed slightly in their assessment of relative cost-effectiveness of the fourth dose: One model found that the incremental cost per DALY averted of the fourth dose was slightly lower than the cost per DALY averted of the first three doses, while the other model estimated a slightly higher cost per DALY averted for the fourth dose compared to three doses. Consistent with previous analyses, both three-dose and four-dose schedules were found to be highly cost-effective in moderate and high transmission settings for nearly all malaria-endemic countries in sub-Saharan Africa.

Feasibility

The recommended four-dose schedule is feasible to implement and delivers substantial health impact, even with suboptimal levels of fourth-dose coverage. Completing a three-dose schedule within the first year of life would be more achievable for individual children than completing a four-dose schedule that extends into the second or third year of life. However, most countries provide routine childhood vaccinations in the second year of life, including the second dose of measles-containing vaccine, and efforts are ongoing to improve uptake at those visits. WHO promotes aligning the fourth malaria vaccine dose with other second-year-of-life vaccines.

Although a three-dose schedule has not been implemented programmatically outside of clinical trials, it is reasonable to assume that if the MVIP countries had implemented a three-dose schedule, they would have achieved coverage levels similar to those observed for the third dose within the four-dose schedule (i.e. around 80%) since the timing of the first three doses is identical in both schedules. Consulted ministry of health officials cautioned that national immunization programmes and ministries of health risk losing credibility and public confidence if they change from a four-dose schedule to a less effective three-dose schedule after health workers and caregivers have been informed that four doses are needed for the best protection (as shown by the data). Experts from national immunization programmes emphasized that implementing different schedules within a country is not operationally feasible.

Acceptability

Consulted ministry of health officials stated that a four-dose schedule that clearly provides higher protection is more acceptable and preferable for both the ministries of health and target population over one that results in lower protection (three-dose schedule). National immunization and malaria control programme managers acknowledged the challenging economic context and high cost as the main barrier to a four-dose schedule.

They reported that, from a caregiver perspective, the undesirable effects of a three-dose schedule (lower protection against severe malaria and death) would outweigh the desirable effects (fewer vaccinations, lower cost and less time for travel to access vaccination) compared to a four-dose schedule.

There was a strong request from consulted ministry of health programme managers that implementing countries, guided by their respective national immunization technical advisory groups, should have the

final decision on which schedule to adopt. Consulted ministry of health programme managers emphasized that changing to or introducing a three-dose schedule could undermine trust in the immunization programme and government and could compromise vaccine acceptability; if such a change were recommended, investments would be needed for communication, stakeholder engagement, community sensitization, revision of materials and guidance, and health worker training in advance of any schedule change.

Equity

Overall, access to additional malaria prevention through vaccination is expected to increase global health equity, specifically by preventing morbidity and mortality in populations with significant disadvantage. High coverage with malaria vaccines could serve the purpose of reducing inequities in access to malaria control interventions. While a three-dose schedule would seem to achieve this goal by ensuring that more children receive malaria vaccination, the evidence indicates that a four-dose schedule provides substantially greater protection against severe malaria than a three-dose schedule.

Based on RTS,S/AS01 MVIP cross-sectional household survey results, a three-dose schedule would not seem to increase country-level inequities compared to a four-dose schedule in terms of coverage of the malaria vaccine, other childhood vaccines, or ITN use, or care-seeking behaviour for fever.

Mathematical modelling estimated that, within similar transmission levels and a fixed number of vaccine doses, providing more children with a three-dose schedule did not yield higher (or lower) population health impact or cost savings than vaccinating fewer children with a four-dose schedule. However, increased disease burden is sometimes observed when the 4th dose was removed from areas with higher transmission to vaccinate additional children in lower transmission settings with a three-dose schedule (who were previously without access to malaria vaccines).

Consultations with programme managers indicated that changing to or introducing a three-dose schedule may be viewed with distrust by the community as it would be perceived as compromising the level of protection and diluting impact within the population.

Conclusions and recommendations for SAGE and MPAG consideration

Information from all available research and programme evaluations provides strong evidence that the four-dose vaccine schedule for RTS,S/AS01 is superior to the three-dose schedule in preventing clinical and severe malaria.

A four-dose schedule provides higher protection against clinical and severe malaria than a three-dose schedule and should remain the recommendation for use. The incremental effectiveness of the fourth dose against severe malaria is substantial. Although the delivery of a three-dose schedule would be simpler and less costly, these factors do not outweigh the substantial clinical benefit provided by a fourth dose. WHO recommends that countries align the timing of the fourth vaccine dose with the timing of other vaccines administered in the second year of life, thereby reducing the additional delivery burden.

Previous WHO recommendations to reduce the number of doses for other vaccines (e.g. pneumococcal conjugate vaccine, human papillomavirus vaccine) have been based on data indicating that fewer vaccine doses would provide similar effectiveness to that of the originally recommended number of doses. This is not the case for RTS,S/AS01, as evidence from the Phase 3 trial shows that the four-dose schedule has a 26% incremental effectiveness in reducing clinical malaria above that provided by the three-dose schedule, and evidence from the MVIP case-control study shows that the four-dose schedule has a 30% incremental effectiveness in reducing severe malaria above that provided by three doses.

Evidence demonstrates that three vaccine doses for children living in areas of perennial malaria transmission provides better protection against clinical and severe malaria than no vaccination; a three-

dose schedule is safe, with continued protection if a fourth dose is missed. However, protection against both clinical and severe malaria is substantially higher with four doses than with three doses.

Children living in areas of conflict or where the delivery of vaccines in the second year of life is not operationally feasible can benefit from a three-dose schedule until obstacles to the delivery of the fourth dose are resolved.

Although there are no data comparing a three-dose to a four-dose schedule for R21/Matrix-M, because of the similarity of the vaccine construct to that of RTS,S/AS01, the Working Group considers the conclusions based on RTS,S/AS01 evidence as applicable to both vaccines.

Given the continued threat of malaria to young children as a leading cause of childhood death in Africa, and given the recent reduction in global financial support for malaria control, the malaria vaccine manufacturers are strongly encouraged to reduce vaccine prices, and Gavi is encouraged to advance market-shaping activities so that children at risk can benefit from the best vaccine schedule.

1. Introduction and purpose of this document

The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends malaria vaccines (RTS,S/AS01 and R21/Matrix-M) for the prevention of *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria in children living in malaria-endemic areas, prioritizing areas of moderate and high transmission (1). Malaria vaccines should be provided in a four-dose schedule in children from 5 months of age for the reduction of malaria illness and death. Depending on a local assessment of feasibility and cost-effectiveness, a fifth dose, given one year after the fourth dose, may be provided in areas of highly seasonal transmission or where malaria risk remains high during the third year of life and beyond.

As of 1 September 2025, 22 countries are implementing the malaria vaccine through their national childhood immunization programme – primarily at the subnational level – as part of their malaria control strategy. All countries, but one, have adopted a four-dose schedule, with the first three doses administered to children in the first year of life and the fourth dose given in the second year of life.

The *Framework for policy decision on RTS,S/AS01 malaria vaccine* (2), endorsed by the Strategic Advisory Group of Experts on Immunization (SAGE) and Malaria Policy Advisory Group (MPAG) in 2019, proposed a stepwise approach to evidence review and malaria vaccine policy development. The framework recognized that additional data on the value of the fourth dose would become available through the evaluation of the Malaria Vaccine Implementation Programme (MVIP) and could inform refinements to the original WHO recommendations on malaria vaccines, including the consideration of a three-dose schedule. Additional exploration and analyses of the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial data, as well as the recent completion of a RTS,S/AS01 case–control study nested within the MVIP’s pilot evaluations in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi, have provided the opportunity to review whether a three-dose schedule has comparable impact to a four-dose schedule – enough to be considered an alternative to a four-dose schedule in some contexts.

Recent updates to the recommended schedules for the human papillomavirus (HPV) vaccine and pneumococcal conjugate vaccine (PCV), based on SAGE reviews, have introduced options for fewer doses. These changes offer useful precedents for understanding the vaccine policy process and assessing feasibility and acceptability among ministries of health and target populations. However, a key distinction is that dose reductions for the HPV vaccine and PCV are not expected to compromise efficacy or impact, while this review of evidence shows that three doses of malaria vaccine provide lower efficacy and impact than the currently recommended four-dose schedule.

A three-dose schedule is not being considered in areas of highly seasonal transmission because there are limited data on the vaccine efficacy of three doses in such settings. Available data indicate that additional vaccine doses provide substantial added benefit, and children living in these areas are typically at risk of severe malaria until an older age than children living in areas of moderate or high perennial transmission.

The specific policy questions for perennial malaria transmission (including low transmission) settings are as follows:

- Is a three-dose malaria vaccine schedule safe and effective?
- Should a three-dose malaria vaccine schedule be considered as an alternative to a four-dose schedule in some contexts?

To address these questions, the SAGE/MPAG Working Group on Malaria Vaccines (see list of members and terms of reference in section 10) reviewed the relevant evidence and followed the key steps involved in creating evidence-based SAGE recommendations, including a systematic review of evidence contributing to the following PICO (population, intervention, comparator, outcome) question: In children living in areas of perennial transmission, what are the effects on clinical malaria, severe malaria, severe

malaria hospitalization, mortality and safety of administering three doses of malaria vaccines compared to the effects of administering the currently recommended four doses of malaria vaccine (first to third doses provided a minimum of four weeks apart; fourth dose at 6–18 months after the third dose)? The Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) approach was used to assess the quality of evidence reviewed. In addition to assessing the benefits and harms of each option, the following elements were assessed to inform potential updates to the guidance on malaria vaccines:

- disease epidemiology;
- data on the value of the fourth dose, including findings from the recently completed RTS,S/AS01 MVIP case–control study nested within the pilot evaluations, findings from the cluster-randomized pilot evaluations, and previously available findings from the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial and its extended follow-up;
- relative importance of the desirable and undesirable effects;
- equity considerations;
- feasibility and resource implications;
- values and preferences, including acceptability by programme managers and the target population;
- other contextual considerations, including opportunities for health systems strengthening;
- modelling estimates of the impact and cost-effectiveness of three- and four-dose schedules across various settings and under different assumptions.

This document summarizes the evidence and information reviewed and presents the recommendations developed by the SAGE/MPAG Working Group on Malaria Vaccines in response to the policy questions. The evidence-to-recommendation table is available in Annex 1 and the GRADE table is given in Annex 2.

2. Background

SAGE and MPAG have jointly reviewed evidence on malaria vaccines during three previous sessions: in October 2015, when they recommended pilot implementation of RTS,S/AS01; in October 2021, when they supported the first WHO recommendation on the use of malaria vaccines (RTS,S/AS01) to prevent *P. falciparum* in children; and in September 2023, when they reviewed the R21/Matrix-M vaccine and recommended its inclusion in an updated WHO recommendation. For a detailed discussion of malaria epidemiology, parasites and pathogenesis, and immune response to malaria infection, please refer to the 2021 *Full evidence report on the RTS,S/AS01 malaria vaccine* (3).

2.1 Disease burden of malaria and epidemiological considerations

Malaria remains one of the leading causes of childhood morbidity and mortality, with the highest burden in Africa. In 2023, approximately 263 million cases and 597 000 deaths were attributed to malaria – 432 000 in young African children (4). Almost all malaria deaths are caused by *P. falciparum*, and approximately 95% of cases and deaths occur in sub-Saharan Africa – mostly in children under 5 years of age.

While the global malaria mortality rate has generally declined over the past two decades – from 28.5 to 13.7 deaths per 100 000 population at risk between 2000 and 2023 – case incidence has remained largely unchanged since 2015; there were more cases and deaths in 2023 than in 2015 (4). In 2023, the number of malaria cases increased by 11 million compared to 2022, while estimated malaria deaths declined only

marginally – from 600 000 to 597 000 – highlighting a trajectory that remains markedly off track to meet the targets of the WHO *Global technical strategy for malaria 2016–2030* (5). The increased use of malaria prevention tools, along with the addition of new tools and strategies, is necessary to further reduce malaria-associated deaths.

The age distribution and total incidence of uncomplicated malaria, severe malaria and malaria-associated deaths can differ by transmission setting, occurring at earlier or later ages (see Fig. 1). In many endemic areas, malaria parasite transmission occurs throughout the year, often with seasonal variation in intensity. The intensity of malaria transmission is usually heterogeneous within a country; there may be areas with very high transmission where malaria is a prominent cause of childhood mortality, areas with variable transmission where sporadic epidemics affect all age groups, and areas with little or no malaria transmission. In areas of high malaria transmission, young children frequently experience multiple episodes of clinical malaria each year, even while using available malaria control tools. In areas of highly seasonal malaria transmission, where half of childhood malaria deaths occur, transmission is primarily limited to four or five months per year, largely influenced by rainfall patterns.

Natural immunity to malaria is acquired gradually with repeated exposure to *Plasmodium* infection. In young infants living in areas of moderate and high malaria transmission, maternally acquired immunity wanes during the first six months of life. The pattern of illness and mortality can vary widely by transmission intensity and seasonality. With increasing age, there is progressive protection – first against severe malaria and ensuing mortality, then against uncomplicated malaria, and, much more slowly and very rarely, against asymptomatic parasitaemia (6). Unfortunately, many children die from malaria before they have developed immunity. To target the deployment of malaria interventions effectively, it is useful to understand the age pattern of cases and deaths, which varies across malaria transmission settings.

In areas of moderate and high transmission, most clinical malaria cases (uncomplicated and severe) occur in children under 5 years of age, while malaria mortality rates begin to fall by around 2 years of age (7, 8). In areas of low malaria transmission, there may be a more even distribution of cases across ages, but mortality remains concentrated in young children. In areas of highly seasonal malaria transmission, acquired immunity may take longer to develop, causing substantial morbidity in children up to 5 years of age or beyond.

Fig. 1. Percentage of uncomplicated clinical malaria, hospital admissions with malaria, and malaria-diagnosed deaths per month of age in children under 10 years of age, by transmission intensity and seasonality of malaria transmission (7)

Ti: transmission intensity

Across all transmission settings, young children carry the highest burden of hospital admissions with malaria (median age: 17 months in high transmission settings, and 36 months in low or highly seasonal transmission settings). Malaria-related deaths tend to be concentrated in even younger children: An analysis of data from seven demographic surveillance sites in areas of perennial transmission in sub-Saharan Africa found that the peak age of malaria mortality was generally less than 1 year of age (9). Studies have shown that across all disease severities (uncomplicated malaria, severe malaria and malaria mortality), the age of peak incidence tends to be lower in perennial transmission settings than in highly seasonal areas due to the less frequent malaria exposure and slower development of natural immunity in highly seasonal areas (7, 8). An analysis of 21 studies in 10 countries across sub-Saharan Africa found that, in areas of high perennial transmission, the median age for malaria mortality was 12 months of age (interquartile range [IQR]: 6–22), compared to 17 months of age (IQR: 7–36) in areas of moderate perennial transmission (7). This can shift to slightly older ages in seasonal areas, with a median age of 15 months (IQR: 8–29) in areas of high transmission with marked seasonality and 28 months (IQR: 15–51) in areas of moderate transmission with marked seasonality. Most malaria prevention strategies are therefore directed towards protecting vulnerable young children to diminish their exposure and risk of death from or associated with malaria.

2.2 Current status of malaria prevention and control measures

All malaria prevention interventions are only partially protective. Higher impact can be achieved by introducing a mix of the different WHO-recommended interventions, determined by the country through subnational tailoring considering the local context (4, 10, 11).

In most African countries, substantial malaria prevention and control efforts have been implemented, including the widespread deployment of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) – pyrethroid, pyrethroid-piperonyl-butoxide, or dual active ingredient nets (recommended in areas of high pyrethroid resistance); indoor residual spraying (IRS) of insecticides in some settings; chemoprevention strategies targeting high-risk groups such as pregnant women or young children living in areas of highly seasonal malaria transmission (seasonal malaria chemoprevention [SMC]); and prompt diagnosis and treatment using quality-assured rapid diagnostic tests and artemisinin-based combination therapies. Chemoprevention for children living in perennial settings (perennial malaria chemoprevention [PMC]) is recommended but has been introduced only in limited areas, as have other chemoprevention strategies.

Gaps in access to and use of malaria prevention tools hinder malaria control. In 2023, 73% of households in sub-Saharan Africa had at least one ITN, but only 59% of children reportedly slept under an ITN (4). The use of ITNs can reduce the incidence of uncomplicated malaria by about half,¹ severe malaria by 44%,² and malaria prevalence in children under 5 by 17% (12);³ however, in many areas, malaria transmission and burden remain high even with good coverage of ITNs or IRS(4). Likewise, the scale-up of SMC in areas of highly seasonal malaria transmission has been an important success, resulting in good impact (13). However, residual malaria remains: In many areas where ITNs and SMC are now deployed, malaria remains the leading cause of death and hospitalization in young children, highlighting the need for additional interventions (4). A malaria vaccine (RTS,S/AS01) was introduced through a pilot programme in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi between 2019 and 2023 and was shown to reduce hospitalized severe malaria by 22% and to reduce all-cause mortality (excluding injury) by 13% (14).⁴ This impact was measured even though these settings had good uptake of other malaria control interventions (ITNs or IRS, access to diagnosis and highly effective treatment). Malaria vaccines have been rolled out more broadly across African countries since 2024, mostly in phased sub-national introductions, with 22 countries now offering malaria vaccines as part of their childhood immunization programme.

Malaria prevention and control measures recommended by WHO (as of August 2025) are summarized in Table 1 (10).

¹ Pooled estimate from five randomized-controlled trials with follow-up periods of 15 weeks, 10 months, one year (two studies), and two years

² Pooled estimate from two studies with follow-up periods of one year and two years

³ Pooled estimate from six randomized-controlled trials with follow-up periods of six months (two studies), 10 months, one year (two studies) and two years

⁴ Mwapasa V, Asante, KP, Milligan P, Akech S, Oduro A, Mathanga D, et al. The impact of introducing the RTS,S/AS01E malaria vaccine delivered through routine immunisation programmes on mortality in young children: 46-month evaluation of cluster-randomised deployment of the vaccine in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi. Not yet published (as of 1 September 2025).

Table 1. Summary of WHO-recommended malaria prevention and control measures (10)

Prevention – vector control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)^a • indoor residual spraying (IRS)^a • larviciding^a • spatial emanators for indoor use^a • house screening^a
Prevention – chemotherapy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy (IPTp) • seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) • perennial malaria chemoprevention (PMC)^a – formerly intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in infants • post-discharge malaria chemoprevention (PDMC)^a • intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in school-aged children (IPTsc)^a • mass drug administration (MDA)^a
Prevention – vaccine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • malaria vaccines for children
Case management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • parasitological diagnosis (using rapid diagnostic testing or microscopy) • treatment of uncomplicated malaria (artemisinin-based combination therapies) • management of severe malaria

^a WHO has issued conditional recommendations for some malaria prevention and control measures; consult the *WHO guidelines for malaria (10)* for more information on specific recommendations.

Several factors have contributed to the slow progress in reducing the global malaria burden, including drug and insecticide resistance; incomplete access to and use of available malaria control interventions; and a limit in the reduction that can be achieved with available tools. Additional challenges include climate change affecting vector distribution and transmission intensity, as well as parasite gene deletions that impact case detection and may delay treatment. The spread of invasive vector species that transmit malaria effectively in urban centres is complicating control efforts in some areas.

Even before the disruptions in donor support in 2025, funding for malaria control was already falling short of global targets. In 2022, global investments in malaria control reached only US\$ 4.1 billion – well below the WHO Global Technical Strategy target of US\$ 7.8 billion (5,15). This gap widened further in 2023, with total investments remaining stagnant at around US\$ 4 billion, despite a revised target of US\$ 8.3 billion (4). More recently, the unpredictable global health funding landscape has threatened to further derail the gains made in malaria control. Global malaria partners project that the 2025 disruptions to commodity supply for malaria control caused by reduced funding to the United States President’s Malaria Initiative and resulting financing gaps may lead to a 12.5% increase in clinical cases (14.6 million cases) and a 39.1% increase in mortality, resulting in an estimated 105 000 additional deaths by the end of 2025 (16).

With progress in malaria control stalled, the world is not on track to achieve the targets to reduce malaria morbidity and mortality set forth in the Global Technical Strategy (5). In 2019, the WHO Strategic Advisory Group on Malaria Eradication concluded that eradication would not be possible by 2050, even with the full scale-up of current interventions. The group highlighted the pivotal role of effective malaria vaccines in achieving elimination. It was in this context of stalled progress, ongoing implementation challenges, the partial efficacy of available interventions and biological threats to current prevention approaches that, in

2021, WHO recommended the use of malaria vaccines as an important new tool for malaria prevention in children.

To achieve the highest impact and save the most lives with limited available resources, WHO supports countries in using subnational tailoring to determine the best package of malaria interventions and strategies for different subnational settings. Subnational tailoring involves the use of local data and contextual information to determine the most effective mix of interventions and strategies for a specific geographical area, aiming to achieve the maximum impact on transmission and disease burden within a specific resource envelope (11).

2.3 WHO malaria vaccine recommendation and status update

2.3.1 WHO recommendation on malaria vaccines (2023)

WHO recommends the use of malaria vaccines for the prevention of *P. falciparum* malaria in children living in malaria-endemic areas, prioritizing areas of moderate and high transmission (1, 10). However, countries may also consider providing the vaccine in low transmission settings. Decisions on expanding malaria vaccination to low transmission settings should be considered at country level on the basis of the overall malaria control strategy, affordability, cost-effectiveness, and programmatic considerations such as whether the inclusion of such areas would simplify delivery (see Box 1 for WHO definitions of transmission settings).

Malaria vaccines should be provided as part of a comprehensive malaria control strategy.

Malaria vaccines should be provided in a four-dose schedule starting from 5 months of age.

- The minimum interval between any doses is four weeks; however, to achieve prolonged protection, the fourth dose should be given 6–18 months after the third dose.
- Countries may choose to give the first vaccine dose earlier than 5 months of age on the basis of operational considerations, to increase coverage or impact.
- To improve coverage, there can be flexibility in the timing of the fourth dose, including by aligning it with vaccines given in the second year of life.
- Alternatively, because vaccine efficacy is highest in the first months after vaccination, the fourth dose can be given just prior to seasonal peaks in malaria transmission to optimize vaccine efficacy.
- A fifth dose may be given in areas of highly seasonal transmission or where severe malaria risk remains high in the third year of life or beyond.

At the time of vaccine introduction, catch-up vaccination can be considered in children up to 5 years of age, subject to local epidemiology and age of high risk, feasibility, affordability and vaccine availability. In many countries with high perennial transmission, the age of highest risk of severe malaria and malaria-associated deaths is under 3 years, while in areas of highly seasonal malaria, the age of highest risk may be extended.

In areas of highly seasonal malaria transmission or perennial malaria transmission with seasonal peaks, countries may consider providing the vaccine using an age-based or seasonal approach. Alternatively, countries could consider a hybrid of these approaches, giving the first three doses through age-based administration and subsequent annual doses just before the malaria season.

Both malaria vaccines (RTS,S/AS01 and R21/Matrix-M) are considered to be safe and well tolerated. There is a small risk of febrile seizures within seven days (mainly within 2–3 days) of vaccination. As with any vaccine introduction, proper planning and training of staff to conduct appropriate education of caregivers and pharmacovigilance should take place beforehand.

Any additional visits needed to administer the malaria vaccine are opportunities to provide other integrated malaria control and preventive health services. Efforts should be made to take advantage of these visits to catch up on missed vaccinations, administer vitamin A, carry out deworming, provide ITNs and other preventive interventions, and remind parents and/or caregivers of the importance of continuing to use an ITN every night, using other malaria preventive measures as recommended, and seeking prompt diagnosis and treatment for a child with fever.

Malaria vaccines may be administered simultaneously with other childhood vaccines.

The choice of malaria vaccine product to be used in a country should be based on product characteristics and programmatic considerations, as well as vaccine supply and long-term affordability. The malaria vaccination series for each child should be completed with the same product whenever feasible. However, if the product used for a previous dose is unavailable or unknown, the series should be completed with either of the available WHO-recommended malaria vaccines. Restarting the vaccine series is not recommended.

Box 1. WHO definitions of *P. falciparum* malaria transmission settings

Note: These thresholds are indicative and should not be regarded as absolutes for determining the applicability of WHO recommendations for malaria interventions.

High transmission settings are those with an approximate annual parasite incidence^a greater than 450 cases per 1000 population or a *P. falciparum* prevalence rate in children aged 2–10 years (PfPR₂₋₁₀) greater than 35%.

Moderate transmission settings are those with an annual parasite incidence between 250 and 450 cases per 1000 population or between 10% and 35% PfPR₂₋₁₀.

Low transmission settings are those with an annual parasite incidence between 100 and 250 cases per 1000 population or between 1% and 10% PfPR₂₋₁₀.

^a number of new parasitologically confirmed malaria cases per 1000 population per year

Source: WHO guidelines for malaria – 13 August 2025 (10)

2.3.2 Recommended malaria vaccines

In October 2021, WHO recommended the first malaria vaccine, RTS,S/AS01, for the prevention of *P. falciparum* malaria in children. The recommendation was based on evidence from clinical trials and the MVIP conducted between 2019 and 2023 in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi. The MVIP was a large WHO-coordinated pilot introduction of RTS,S/AS01 vaccine with a robust evaluation component (the pilot evaluations). The vaccine was introduced using a cluster-randomized design to measure the safety of the vaccine in routine use, as well as its feasibility and impact. During 46 months of hospital and community-based mortality surveillance, the pilot evaluations showed that the RTS,S/AS01 vaccine had a good safety profile, that it could reach children through the routine immunization systems, and that roll-out of the vaccine resulted in high impact, with a 13% reduction in all-cause mortality (excluding injury) in children age-eligible for vaccination – during a period of scale-up when approximately 71% of children had received three doses of malaria vaccine and only approximately 40% of children had received the fourth dose(14).⁵

⁵ Mwapasa V, Asante, KP, Milligan P, Akech S, Oduro A, Mathanga D, et al. The impact of introducing the RTS,S/AS01E

Therefore, the results showed that important impact could be achieved even without high uptake of the fourth vaccine dose, which was provided at around 2 years of age (but now is recommended during the second year of life, with most countries aligning the fourth dose with the timing of other second-year-of-life vaccines) (14).

In 2021, published findings (17) showed that seasonal vaccination with RTS,S/AS01, given in a three-dose series just before the high transmission season followed by a pre-season dose given annually during the subsequent two transmission seasons (up to five total doses), was non-inferior to SMC; when added to SMC, the RTS,S/AS01 + SMC combination substantially reduced the incidence of clinical malaria, severe malaria and deaths from malaria in young children over a three-year period compared to either intervention alone. SAGE/MPAG considered these data in the 2021 RTS,S/AS01 evidence review and included a recommendation for an optional fifth dose in areas of highly seasonal transmission or perennial transmission with seasonal peaks, using a seasonal or hybrid delivery approach.

Similar to RTS,S/AS01, the R21/Matrix-M malaria vaccine is indicated for the reduction of malaria due to *P. falciparum* in infants and young children. It uses the same pre-erythrocytic target antigen: the *P. falciparum* circumsporozoite protein. In October 2023, WHO recommended R21/Matrix-M for the prevention of *P. falciparum* malaria in children living in endemic areas, based on data from clinical trials demonstrating the vaccine's safety and efficacy against clinical malaria when administered through either an age-based or seasonal vaccination approach (1). The trials include an ongoing Phase 3 clinical trial in five study sites across four countries in sub-Saharan Africa (Dandé and Nanoro, Burkina Faso; Bagamoyo, United Republic of Tanzania; Kilifi, Kenya; and Bougouni, Mali). At the time of the WHO recommendation, Phase 3 trial data up to 18 months of follow-up were available for review. Further details can be found in the 2023 *Full evidence report on the R21/Matrix-M malaria vaccine* (18). The Phase 3 trial continues until 2027, and as of 1 September 2025, two years of follow-up data are available.

Both vaccines are pre-erythrocytic vaccines using similar vaccine constructs (recombinant subunit as virus-like particle) and adjuvants (saponin-based). The vaccines also have the same target antigen, target population, mechanism of action and recommended dose schedule. Clinical trials have demonstrated that both vaccines are safe and effective, but the two vaccines have not been directly compared in a head-to-head trial. Therefore, it is not possible to determine the relative efficacy of the vaccines based on available data.

2.3.3 Status of malaria vaccine implementation

The RTS,S/AS01 malaria vaccine was first introduced into childhood immunization programmes in selected areas of Ghana, Kenya and Malawi by the respective ministries of health in 2019, as part of the WHO-coordinated MVIP. Following the WHO recommendation for the broader use of the vaccine, issued in October 2021, vaccine implementation was expanded to MVIP comparator areas across all three countries.

Demand for malaria vaccines is high. More than 30 African countries have formally expressed interest in introducing the vaccine. However, initial global supply constraints limited the pace and scope of introductions immediately following the WHO recommendation. A *Framework for the allocation of limited malaria vaccine supply* (19), developed by WHO, was applied to guide the equitable and transparent distribution of available doses. In seeking to compare malaria burden across countries, the framework gave priority to subnational areas with the greatest need, based on malaria transmission intensity and

malaria vaccine delivered through routine immunisation programmes on mortality in young children: 46-month evaluation of cluster-randomised deployment of the vaccine in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi. Not yet published (as of 1 September 2025).

child mortality rates. In mid-2023, the 18 million doses of RTS,S/AS01 available for the 2023–2025 period were committed to 12 countries in Africa, including the three MVIP countries, enabling the latter to continue vaccine implementation (20).

Building on this prioritization, the first subnational introductions in non-pilot countries began in January 2024. These introductions marked the start of a phased malaria vaccine roll-out across Africa, supported by Gavi, the Vaccine Alliance. A second WHO-recommended and prequalified vaccine, R21/Matrix-M, became available in late 2023, resulting in increased vaccine supply that was sufficient to meet demand. Thereafter, the pace of introductions accelerated. By 1 September 2025, 22 countries in Africa had adopted malaria vaccines in their childhood immunization programmes, using either RTS,S/AS01 or R21/Matrix M: Benin, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Côte d’Ivoire, Chad, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ghana, Guinea, Kenya, Liberia, Malawi, Mali, Mozambique, Niger, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, South Sudan, Sudan, Togo and Uganda (Fig. 2). Over 38 million doses of vaccines have been delivered by the United Nations Children’s Fund (UNICEF) to these countries to meet the needs of a growing cumulative annual target population, currently over 9 million children (21).

Fig. 2. Status of malaria vaccine roll-out, 1 September 2025

To date, all but one implementing country (Mali) has adopted a four-dose, age-based vaccination schedule (Fig. 3). Countries have chosen to provide the first three doses in the first year of life between 5 and 9 months of age. The fourth dose is typically administered during an existing vaccination visit during the second year of life – most often at 15, 16 or 18 months of age – depending on the country context. Only three countries (Cameroon, Kenya and Malawi) administer the fourth dose as a separate vaccination visit close to or at 2 years of age. Mali, which experiences high-intensity, highly seasonal malaria transmission, has adopted a five-dose hybrid schedule, with the first three doses administered based on a child’s age, and the fourth and fifth doses administered annually just before the high transmission season.

Fig. 3. Countries’ malaria vaccine schedule choices (top row: age in months for each dose)

Country	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	
Benin						1	2		3										4						
Burkina Faso					1	2	3								4										
Burundi						1	2		3										4						
Cameroon						1	2		3															4	
Central African Republic						1	2		3								4								
Chad						1	2		3						4										
Côte d'Ivoire						1		2	3						4										
Democratic Republic of the Congo						1	2	3							4										
Ghana						1	2		3										4						
Guinea					1	2	3								4										
Kenya						1	2		3															4	
Liberia					1	2	3								4										
Malawi						1	2	3															4		
Mali*						1	2	3																	
Mozambique						1	2		3										4						
Niger						1	2	3																	
Nigeria					1	2	3								4										
Sierra Leone						1	2	3											4						
South Sudan					1	2	3												4						
Sudan					1	2	3												4						
Togo					1	2	3								4										
Uganda						1	2	3											4						

*In the hybrid approach, children return for a seasonal dose (doses 4 and 5) each year just before the high transmission season (and at least 6 months after dose 3)

All vaccine introductions to date have benefited from Gavi support. Gavi’s current funding guidelines specify that support can be requested for introduction of the malaria vaccine into a country’s immunization programme in a four- or five-dose schedule in areas of moderate and high malaria transmission, in line with WHO recommendations on where to prioritize vaccine use (22). With sufficient vaccine supply available from the two manufacturers, countries can now apply to Gavi to expand the scope of malaria vaccine implementation beyond the initial limited areas identified under the *Framework for the allocation of limited malaria vaccine supply* (19). However, given the constrained financial resources for vaccine procurement and the need to ensure sustainable support over time, Gavi is currently limiting its support for malaria vaccine implementation to geographical areas (selected by the countries) representing no more than 85% of the total target population of children living in moderate and high transmission settings. Consequently, children residing in districts with comparable malaria burden – moderate or high transmission – are excluded from vaccine access unless those geographical areas are supported through domestic financing or alternative external funding sources. WHO provides technical support to countries as they consider where to target malaria vaccine doses as part of a mix of malaria interventions. Although Gavi replenishment efforts for the 2026–2030 strategic period have secured substantial commitments – over US\$ 9 billion pledged towards the US\$ 11.9 billion target – a funding gap remains as of August 2025 (23). Consequently, the Gavi Board is considering how to prioritize resources, which will likely involve further reductions in the scope of support for the malaria vaccine roll-out.

2.4 Vaccine schedule modifications

Manufacturers’ labels are often based on the initial vaccination schedules used in the clinical trials that do not necessarily reflect ease of programmatic implementation and population-level protection. Post-marketing studies or implementation experience may generate evidence that is sufficiently robust to support use of a vaccine beyond its label use indication. WHO may issue recommendations that lead to “off-label” public health use of a vaccine, guided by clear public health benefit and benefit–risk analysis. Many national immunization technical advisory groups (NITAGs) consider WHO’s advice to formulate their

own country-specific recommendations (24).

The current WHO position paper on malaria vaccines (1) already contains recommendations (such as on the interval between third and fourth doses) that differ from the approved labelling on the vaccine products. Therefore, consideration of a three-dose malaria vaccine schedule as an alternative to the recommended four-dose schedule would continue to fall under off-label use.

There are recent examples of recommendations to reduce dosing schedules for other antigens – including HPV vaccine and PCV – for “off-label” public health use (see Box 2 and Box 3). In both cases, the alternative schedule is limited to some settings and circumstances. Another important note – and a key difference to the malaria vaccine – is that the reduced schedule options were assessed to be comparable or, in the case of PCV, non-inferior to the alternative schedule in terms of protection.

Box 2: More information on HPV vaccine schedule change

The WHO position paper (2022 update) on HPV vaccines (255) indicates that the current evidence supports the recommendation that a two-dose schedule be used in the primary target group from 9 years of age and for all older age groups for which HPV vaccines are licensed. In April 2022, SAGE reviewed evidence on the efficacy of a single-dose HPV schedule. The updated position paper indicates that a single-dose schedule can be used as an alternative, off-label schedule based on the following considerations:

- Given the current evidence of comparable efficacy and duration of protection to a two-dose schedule, a one-dose schedule may offer programmatic advantages, be more efficient and affordable, and contribute to improved coverage.
- From a public health perspective, the single-dose schedule can offer substantial benefits that outweigh the potential risk of lower levels of protection if efficacy wanes over time.
- This off-label single-dose option for routine and multi-age cohort catch-up vaccination was considered because it provides comparable and high levels of individual protection while, from a public health perspective, being more efficient (fewer doses per cancer case prevented), less resource-intensive and easier to implement than a two-dose schedule.
- This advice applies to those HPV vaccines for which corresponding one-dose data have been collected.

Box 3: More information on PCV schedule change

The WHO position paper (2019 update) on PCV in infants and children under 5 years (26) recommended a three-dose schedule, starting as early as 6 weeks of age. In March 2025, SAGE reviewed evidence on using PCV in a two-dose schedule in settings where pneumococcal transmission had been reduced through the longstanding use of a three-dose schedule or multi-age cohort campaigns. The two-dose schedule (1p+1) is provided as a single primary dose under 1 year of age followed by a booster dose after some time (around 1 year of age). The three-dose schedule uses either three primary doses without a booster dose (3p+0) or two primary doses with a booster dose around 1 year of age (2p+1). The position paper on PCV has not been updated as of early September 2025; however, conclusions and recommendations from the SAGE meeting (27) included the following:

- Evidence from randomized trials showed that while a 1p+1 PCV schedule produced lower immune responses after the primary dose compared to the three-dose schedules, post-booster immunogenicity was similar. No differences in vaccine-type pneumococcal carriage were observed.
- In the Gambia, a large cluster-randomized trial found non-inferior carriage and pneumonia outcomes in 1p+1 versus 3p+0 clusters. In England (United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), five years of data following a switch to 1p+1 showed sustained low rates of vaccine-type invasive disease.

Based on available evidence, SAGE recommended that countries or subnational regions with well established population immunity among children under 5 years, achieved through a mature three-dose PCV programme with high coverage of at least 80%, could consider off-label use of a 1p+1 schedule to reduce costs and number of injections, while remaining prepared to revert if disease control declines.

3. Overview of previously available data and analysis comparing a three-dose to a four-dose schedule

This section summarizes the relevant evidence for comparing a three-dose to a four-dose schedule, drawn from the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial (section 3.1) and its extension study (section 3.2), as well as further MVIP analyses that informed previous WHO malaria vaccine recommendations in 2015 (28) and 2021, and current recommendations from 2023 (1). Additional background and results from these studies are available in the 2021 SAGE/MPAG background paper *Full evidence report on the RTS,S/AS01 malaria vaccine* (3).

The WHO position paper on malaria vaccines recommends a four-dose vaccine schedule, based on the previously available evidence (1). Data from the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial showed that a four-dose schedule resulted in higher vaccine efficacy and longer duration of protection than a three-dose schedule, and a fourth dose was required to maintain protection against severe malaria; the findings suggested that children randomized to receive three vaccine doses experienced rebound severe malaria as vaccine efficacy waned, and the early protection against severe malaria was negated by later cases of severe malaria (29). Rebound malaria is defined here as a period of increased malaria risk after time-limited protection from malaria, relative to children from the same population who did not receive that protection (30). Mathematical modelling predicted that both a three-dose and four-dose schedule results in positive public health impact and were found to have similar cost effectiveness compared to no vaccination, with the fourth dose providing additional incremental impact over three doses (section 3.2.4).

However, the models were unable to reproduce the extent of rebound of severe malaria cases observed in the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial in the three-dose group.

Unlike the RTS,S/AS01 trials, the Phase 2 and ongoing Phase 3 trials of R21/Matrix-M have not included a comparator study group receiving only three doses. As a result, data to directly compare a three-dose schedule of R21/Matrix-M to a four-dose schedule are not available (section 5).

3.1 Rationale for a four-dose schedule based on RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial results

The 2015 WHO recommendation for large-scale pilot implementation studies of RTS,S/AS01, following the Phase 3 clinical trial results, was based on several outstanding questions. One of the concerns addressed in the MVIP (2017–2023) was whether it was operationally feasible to reach children at high coverage with a four-dose schedule (with the fourth dose provided around 2 years of age), and consequently the extent to which the protection demonstrated against clinical and severe malaria in the Phase 3 trial could be replicated when the vaccine was delivered using routine systems. At the time, the fourth dose was felt to be essential because the Phase 3 trial results suggested that three doses alone had no overall effect on the incidence of severe malaria, with the protective effect in the first 18 months balanced by an increase in cases in the period from 18 months to the end of the trial (median of 48 months of follow-up).

The Phase 3 trial results comparing three-dose and four-dose groups are briefly summarized below, with more details available in the previous evidence reports.

3.1.1 Background

The Phase 3 clinical trial of RTS,S/AS01 was conducted over five years (2009–2014) at 11 sites in seven sub-Saharan African countries (Burkina Faso, Gabon, Ghana, Kenya, Malawi, Mozambique, and the United Republic of Tanzania). Participants were randomized 1:1:1 to receive control vaccine, three doses of RTS,S/AS01 plus control vaccine at 18 months after the third dose, or three doses of RTS,S/AS01 plus a fourth dose of RTS,S/AS01 at 18 months after the third dose (29).

The RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial was conducted in settings with improved access to quality care and high coverage and use of ITNs; furthermore, there was very low mortality among children enrolled in the trial compared to unenrolled children living in the same areas (31). The 11 trial sites were located in areas with different intensities of malaria transmission, with two sites with low transmission (Kilifi, Kenya; Korogwe, United Republic of Tanzania), four sites with moderate perennial transmission (Lambarene, Gabon; Lilongwe, Malawi; Manhiça, Mozambique; Bagamoyo, United Republic of Tanzania), four sites with high perennial transmission (Agogo, Ghana; Kintampo, Ghana; Kombewa, Kenya; Siaya, Kenya), and one site with highly seasonal transmission (Nanoro, Burkina Faso).

A total of 15 499 children 5–17 months of age were randomized to the four-dose group, the three-dose group, or the control group, and followed over a median of 48 months of follow-up (IQR: 39–50). The three- and four-dose groups were evaluated together during the first 20 months of follow-up, prior to a fourth dose being administered 18 months after the third dose.

3.1.2 Clinical malaria

From study month 2.5 (two weeks after the third dose) until study end (median follow-up of 48 months), there were 6597 cases of clinical malaria among 2306 children in the three-dose group, and 5691 cases among 2276 children in the four-dose group. The overall efficacy against clinical malaria was 26.2% (95% CI: 20.8–31.2) for three doses and 39% (95% CI: 34.3–43.3) for four doses (29).

Vaccine efficacy waned over time; efficacy against clinical malaria in the three-dose group reached zero

during the interval from month 32 until study end (Fig. 4). In the four-dose group, efficacy increased following the fourth dose and then declined, but remained positive through to the study end.

Fig. 4. Vaccine efficacy against clinical malaria stratified by time period in the 5–17 months age category in the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial (primary case definition, according-to-protocol population). Data provided by GlaxoSmithKline (GSK) on request

Source: Joint Technical Expert Group on Malaria Vaccines background paper 2015 (28)

In pooled analysis, vaccine efficacy against clinical malaria was higher among children randomized to receive four doses compared to those who received three doses. Across the 11 sites, point estimates of vaccine efficacy against clinical malaria were higher in the four-dose groups than in the three-dose groups. However, there were wide and overlapping CIs with variation by transmission intensity (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Vaccine efficacy against all episodes of clinical malaria in the 5–17 month age category (primary case definition, according-to-protocol study population, month 2.5 until study end); A) three-dose schedule; B) four-dose schedule

Note. Sites are ordered based on incidence of clinical malaria with lowest transmission at the top. Data provided by GSK on request. Of note: The Manhiça site is not listed in this according-to-protocol analysis due to a loss of data after administration of vaccine affected by a temperature deviation.

The estimated numbers of cases of clinical malaria averted during a median of 48 months of follow-up were 1363 (95% CI: 995–1797) per 1000 vaccinated children with a three-dose schedule and 1774 (95% CI: 1387–2186) per 1000 vaccinated children with a four-dose schedule. The largest numbers of cases averted per 1000 vaccinated children were at sites with the greatest disease burden, reaching more than 4000 cases averted with three doses and 6500 cases averted with four doses, during a median of 48 months of follow-up. Although the fourth dose resulted in a larger number of additional clinical malaria cases averted compared to three doses in areas of moderate or high malaria transmission, there was little added benefit of the fourth dose in terms of the number of clinical or severe malaria cases averted in areas of low transmission (Fig. 6) (29).

3.1.3 Severe malaria

There were 157 cases of severe malaria among 2336 children in the control group (0.20 per person-years at risk), 159 cases of severe malaria among 2306 children in the three-dose group (0.21 per person-years at risk), and 116 cases among 2276 children in the four-dose group (0.14 per person-years at risk). The overall vaccine efficacy against severe malaria during a median of 48 months of follow-up in the four-dose group was 31.5% (95% CI: 9.3–48.3) compared to -2.2% (95% CI: -31.3–20.4) in the three-dose group. In the three-dose group, the vaccine efficacy in the first 18 months of follow-up (months 2.5 to 20: vaccine efficacy: 37.7%; 95% CI: 18.0–52.6) appeared to be offset by a higher incidence of severe malaria after 18 months compared to the control group (29). This was considered potential rebound – under the assumption that the increased severe malaria among children in the three-dose study group compared to children in the control group was due to limited exposure and less acquired immunity compared to children in the control group who were exposed to more malaria infections.

Fig. 6. Cases of clinical (A) and severe (B) malaria averted at each site during 48 months of follow-up in the 5–17 month age category (intention-to-treat analysis); R3C = three-dose schedule and R3R = four-dose schedule; data are ordered by increasing malaria incidence at each study site

3.2 Further data and analyses following completion of the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial

The 2021 WHO recommendation for wider use of RTS,S/AS01 in moderate and high transmission settings was informed, in part, by the MVIIP results from the first two years of vaccination via the routine immunization systems in Ghana and Malawi, and the first 18 months in Kenya. Approximately 62% of age-eligible children had received at least three vaccine doses, and it was still too early to assess fourth-dose coverage. The recommendation for use was based on clinical trial findings before 2015 and subsequent studies, including one extension to the Phase 3 clinical trial – in three of the 11 sites – that showed children living in areas of perennial moderate to high malaria transmission benefit from three or four doses of the vaccine. The recommendation was supported by information showing that it takes time to attain high coverage of new vaccines, particularly in the second year of life.

The following is a summary of studies and analyses following the completion of the Phase 3 trial that have provided opportunities to revisit the need for a fourth dose.

3.2.1 Long-term follow-up RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 clinical trial

An open-label extension study (2014–2016) followed a subset of children (1739 older children) from three of the 11 Phase 3 trial sites for an additional three years (seven years in total for those first vaccinated at 5–17 months of age). The three sites represented different levels of transmission intensity: Korogwe, United Republic of Tanzania (low transmission); Kombewa, Kenya (high perennial transmission); and Nanoro, Burkina Faso (high, highly seasonal transmission). The primary outcome of interest was the incidence of severe malaria up to seven years post-vaccination; participants were also followed for incidence of clinical malaria. Details on study methods have been published (32).

During the three-year extension, among the 1739 children who were first vaccinated at 5–17 months of age, the overall incidences of clinical malaria per 1000 person-years at risk were 1079 (95% CI: 152–7662) in the four-dose group, 1108 (95% CI: 156–7868) in the three-dose group, and 1016 (95% CI: 143–7213) in the control group; incidences of severe malaria per 1000 person-years at risk were 4 (95% CI: 0–33) in the four-dose group, 7 (95% CI: 1–52) in the three-dose group, and 9 (95% CI: 1–66) in the control group (Fig. 7).

Although there was no significant efficacy against clinical or severe malaria during the additional three years, the benefits documented during the first four years of follow-up were still evident at the end of the seven years: Vaccine efficacy against clinical and severe malaria, respectively, for the four-dose group was 23.7% (95% CI: 15.9–30.7%) and 36.7% (95% CI: 14.6–53.1%), and for the three-dose group was 19.1% (95% CI: 10.8% to 26.7%) and 10.1% (95% CI: -18.1%–31.6%), and any rebound that occurred in the three-dose group was time-limited.

Overall, the extended follow-up study demonstrated that, over the six- to seven-year period following RTS,S/AS01 vaccination, the incidence of severe malaria declined in children, regardless of a three-dose or four-dose schedule.

In one site with intense seasonal transmission (Nanoro), there were more episodes of clinical malaria among vaccinated children than in the control group during the three-year extended follow-up period: Vaccine efficacy against clinical malaria was -30.3% (95% CI: -59.5% to -6.4%) in the four-dose group and -26.0% (95% CI: -56.0% to -6.4%) in the three-dose group. Therefore, in this site with highly seasonal malaria transmission, there was an overall benefit against clinical malaria from vaccination during the entire seven-year follow-up among children who received the four-dose schedule (vaccine efficacy: 13.8%; 95% CI: 3.3–23.1%), while there was no measurable benefit among those who received the three-dose schedule (vaccine efficacy: 7.2%; 95% CI: -4.2–17.5%).

Fig. 7. Incidence of severe malaria in children enrolled at 5–17 months of age in the intention-to-treat population (32)

(A) Korogwe. (B) Kombewa. (C) Nanoro. (D) Overall. M0=time of the first dose administration in the initial study. M20=20 months after the first dose in the initial study. M21=21 months after the first dose in the initial study. Error bars represent 95% CI.

Overall, protection against clinical and severe malaria was higher throughout the seven-year follow-up period among children in the four-dose group compared to those in the three-dose group. Nonetheless, in areas of perennial malaria transmission, children who received three or four doses of RTS,S/AS01 benefited for at least seven years after vaccination, without risk of rebound clinical or severe malaria. Although there was no measurable added protection from vaccination after the first 48 months of follow-up, the impact observed during the first years of protection from the three- or four-dose schedule was not subsequently lost. The results from the Nanoro site imply that in some intensely seasonal settings, where almost all malaria transmission occurs in a 4–5-month period, children may experience a limited period of increased risk of clinical malaria relative to unvaccinated children; children living in highly seasonal areas would more likely benefit from additional malaria vaccine doses – at least a four-dose schedule.

3.2.2 RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 post hoc analyses

Up until the time of the fourth dose (month 20), the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 study treated the groups of children randomized to receive three or four doses as a single group. However, a review of the incidence of severe malaria from first vaccination by study group demonstrated lower severe malaria incidence in the four-dose group before the fourth dose was administered compared to the three-dose group (Fig. 8 and Fig. 9). This unexpected finding was explored in detail, with the conclusion that it was due to chance. Nonetheless, this early divergence may have led to an overestimation of the risk of severe malaria in the three-dose group compared to that in the four-dose group and may have contributed to a potential overestimation of the importance of the fourth dose. Across all groups, the incidence of severe malaria decreased by study month to a low level by the end of the trial (months 48–56), showing that the overall incidence of severe malaria was declining in all groups.

Fig. 8. Incidence per person-year of severe malaria in six-month periods, before and after receiving the fourth dose, in ages 5–17 months (intention-to-treat population)

Source: Modelling groups with permission from GSK. Dotted line represents when the fourth dose was given.

Fig. 9. Cumulative hazard estimates of severe malaria from the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial

Source: Adapted from RTS,S/AS01 case-control results presentation to Data and Safety Monitoring Board (DSMB), 13 May 2025

3.2.3 Evidence from the MVIP

The MVIP – a large pilot programme coordinated by WHO, through which nearly 2 million children received the RTS,S/AS01 vaccine through the routine childhood immunization programmes run by the ministries of health in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi, in settings with good coverage and use of ITNs – showed that vaccine introduction had high impact even with low uptake of the fourth dose. During 46 months of surveillance, a 22% (95% CI: 4–37%) reduction in hospitalized severe malaria and 13% (95% CI: 3–23%) reduction in all-cause mortality in children age-eligible for vaccination were measured; this was during a period of scale-up when on average only 71% of children had received three vaccine doses and 40% had received the fourth vaccine dose (14).⁶ These findings showed that high impact could be reached with low uptake of the fourth dose; however, severe malaria and mortality among children in the comparator areas persisted until 3 years of age before declining substantially, suggesting that even higher impact could be achieved with high uptake of the fourth vaccine dose.

3.2.4 Public health impact modelling based on RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 data

In 2015 and in 2018, the modelling groups at The Kids Research Institute Australia (previously at Swiss Tropical and Public Health Institute) and Imperial College London validated their models with data from the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 extended three-year follow-up study (2014-2016; section 3.2.1). They predicted that over a 15-year period, on a population basis, both a three-dose and four-dose schedule resulted in positive public health impact and were found to have similar cost effectiveness when compared to no vaccination (33/34). The models estimated that most of the public health impact would be driven primarily by the coverage levels of the first three vaccine doses. The fourth dose of vaccine, with modelled delivery at 18 months following the third dose, also provided additional incremental impact. The 2015 and 2018 modelling analyses predicted positive and sustained impact of three doses against severe disease, and therefore did not reproduce the extent of the rebound in severe malaria observed in the three-dose group of the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial (2009 – 2014); this may be explained by a chance occurrence in the Phase 3 trial further explained in section 3.2.2.

3.2.5 Summary of results and analyses prior to RTS,S/AS01 case–control study results

Since the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial (2009–2014) suggested that the fourth dose was needed to maintain vaccine efficacy against severe malaria and to avoid rebound, the following findings have emerged regarding the RTS,S/AS01 three-dose and four-dose schedules:

- Results from seven years of follow-up at three of the 11 RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial sites indicated sustained vaccine efficacy among children randomized to receive three or four doses and showed that any rebound among those who received only three doses was time-limited, bringing into question the value of the fourth dose.
- Review of RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 clinical data showed lower incidence of severe malaria in children randomized to the four-dose group compared to those randomized to the three-dose group, prior to the fourth dose being administered, which may have increased the apparent importance of the fourth dose.
- During 46 months of surveillance in the MVIP, statistically significant impacts against severe malaria and all-cause mortality were observed, despite only 40% of children having received the fourth dose.

⁶ Mwapasa V, Asante, KP, Milligan P, Akech S, Oduro A, Mathanga D, et al. The impact of introducing the RTS,S/AS01E malaria vaccine delivered through routine immunisation programmes on mortality in young children: 46-month evaluation of cluster-randomised deployment of the vaccine in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi. Not yet published (as of 1 September 2025).

4. RTS,S/AS01 case–control study

This section summarizes results from an RTS,S/AS01 case–control study that have become available since the publication of the last WHO position paper. The case–control study compared the effectiveness and safety of three versus four doses.

4.1 Design and methods overview

The overall aim of the RTS,S/AS01 case–control study (2021–2025) was to determine the incremental benefit of the recommended four doses of RTS,S/AS01 over three doses, in the context of vaccine delivery through the routine childhood immunization programmes in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi. The case–control study also sought to obtain additional data on the three safety signals identified in the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial, to supplement findings from the cluster-randomized MVIP pilot evaluations which found no evidence of association with the vaccine (section 4.3).

The RTS,S/AS01 case–control study was nested within the WHO-coordinated MVIP (2019–2023; section 3.2.3). The MVIP evaluated the subnational introduction of the malaria vaccine in moderate and high transmission areas in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi, using randomization of subnational implementation and comparison areas to reduce bias. The pilot evaluations within the MVIP measured population-level effects of vaccine introduction; the estimates of impact and safety were diluted by incomplete vaccine coverage (and to a limited extent by vaccination of some children living in neighbouring areas). The case–control study provided an opportunity to estimate effects (benefits and risks) among vaccinated children, including the value of the fourth vaccine dose.

The case–control study leveraged the sentinel hospital and community-based mortality surveillance systems established by in-country research partners for the MVIP. The case–control study was conducted in the catchment areas of 18 sentinel hospitals (eight in Ghana, six in Kenya, and four in Malawi) and limited to children living in areas where RTS,S/AS01 vaccination had been added to the routine childhood vaccination programme. Cases of severe malaria, meningitis and cerebral malaria were identified at sentinel hospitals where diagnostic procedures had been strengthened. Cases of child death were identified in the community through the MVIP surveillance systems. Cases were eligible for inclusion if, at the time of the event, they were resident in sentinel hospital catchment areas in an area where RTS,S was being implemented, were of an age to be eligible to have received RTS,S/AS01, and were aged under 60 months. At the start of case-control study recruitment, cases aged 6–30 months were eligible in Ghana, 6–37 months in Kenya, and 5–29 months in Malawi; by the end of recruitment, children aged 6–59 months (Ghana and Kenya) or 5–59 months (Malawi) were eligible. Controls, matched to cases by date of birth and geographical location, were identified in the community (four controls for each case). Further background on the surveillance systems established in the MVIP has been published (35).

Data collection for the case–control study commenced in October 2021 and included six months of retrospective recruitment in Ghana and Malawi (but no retrospective recruitment in Kenya). Following the completion of data collection for the evaluation of the pilot introduction of RTS,S/AS01 in July 2023, hospital surveillance for meningitis and severe malaria was maintained in the three countries to identify cases for the case–control study. In addition, mortality surveillance was maintained in Ghana and Malawi, while Kenya had already reached the target sample size for the case–control study mortality endpoint. Case–control study data collection continued through November 2024 in Ghana and Malawi, and through March 2025 in Kenya, to ensure adequate recruitment of cases and controls for the different study endpoints.

4.1.1 Study objectives

The specific objectives of the case–control study were to assess:

- the effect of three doses of RTS,S/AS01 on the incidence of severe malaria during the period until the fourth dose is due;
- the effect of RTS,S/AS01 on the incidence of severe malaria from the time of the fourth dose, comparing (i) children who received four doses to children who received three doses; and (ii) children who received three doses (but did not receive the fourth dose) to children who received zero doses;
- the effect of RTS,S/AS01 on the incidence of meningitis and cerebral malaria; and
- the interaction representing the effect of gender on the association of RTS,S/AS01 with all-cause mortality.

4.1.2 Recruitment of cases and controls

The methods are described in detail in the protocol (NCT05041556) (36).

In brief, for each child with severe malaria or meningitis and each child who died, four control children born within one month of the date of birth of the case were recruited from the neighbourhood of the case's home, going house to house after moving a distance of at least 100 m from the case's home. Controls for each case were recruited shortly after the time the case was detected. The primary analysis was limited to cases and controls with vaccine histories documented in the child's home-based record (HBR) or the clinic register.

4.1.3 Statistical analysis

The analytical approach, including sample size calculations, is described in detail in the RTS,S/AS01 case–control study analysis report (37), also found in Annex 3.

In brief, for safety analyses, vaccine doses were counted in cases and controls if they were received prior to the date the case was admitted to the hospital; for deaths, all documented doses were counted. Vaccine effects were presented in two ways: (i) comparing children who received one, two, three or four doses to unvaccinated children; and (ii) as the incremental effectiveness of each dose, adjusted for the previous doses. Analyses of severe malaria, including cerebral malaria, were adjusted for ITN use, caregiver education, household wealth ranking and child gender. For meningitis, analyses were adjusted for receipt of pentavalent (which protects against diphtheria, tetanus, pertussis, hepatitis B and *Haemophilus influenzae* type b), pneumococcal, and meningococcal A vaccines, the number of children in the household, and the number who shared the same sleeping place. Analyses of all-cause mortality were adjusted for caregiver education, household wealth ranking, child gender and receipt of other vaccines. ITN use was not adjusted for in the all-cause mortality analysis because of the difficulty of determining ITN use before death.

4.2 RTS,S/AS01 case–control study: vaccine effectiveness against severe malaria in children who received three versus four doses

Vaccine doses administered at least 14 days before the event were included in the effectiveness analysis. The index date for the vaccination status in the controls was 14 days before the date of the event. As described above, vaccine effects are presented either as a **cumulative effect** (compared to unvaccinated children) or as an **incremental effect** (compared to previous doses).

The malaria vaccine doses were provided through routine immunization in a four-dose schedule: in Malawi at 5, 6, 7 and 22 months of age; in Ghana at 6, 7, 9 and 24 months of age (fourth dose shifted to

18 months to align with the second dose of measles vaccine as of February 2023); and in Kenya at 6, 7, 9 and 24 months of age.

For the severe malaria analysis, vaccine effectiveness is presented as described below:

- effectiveness of one, two and three doses until the age scheduled for the fourth dose;
- effectiveness of one, two and three doses from the age scheduled for the fourth dose, in children who did not receive the fourth dose;
- effectiveness of the fourth dose;
- effectiveness of three doses in successive time periods after the third dose: within six months of the third dose, 6–18 months after the third dose, and 18 months or more after the third dose, and the effectiveness of the fourth dose in the same time intervals after the fourth dose; these periods were chosen to compare the vaccine efficacy for the same periods as for the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial; and
- effectiveness of one, two, three and four doses of RTS,S/AS01 for the whole study period.

The study recruited 1546 cases of severe malaria (including cerebral malaria) and 6151 controls (Table 2). Among children with documented vaccine histories, 93 cases (7%) and 447 controls (8%) were excluded because the HBRs were replacements;⁷ 1271/1546 (82%) cases with 4736/6151 (77%) matched controls were included in the analyses. Approximately 73% (930/1271) of cases and 79% (3719/4736) of controls had received any dose of RTS,S/AS01. A little over 50% (51%, 653/1271) of cases and 62% (2930/4736) of controls had received the third dose of RTS,S/AS01. A little less than 15% (14%, 183/1271) of cases and 19% (905/4736) of controls had received the fourth dose of RTS,S/AS01. The characteristics of the severe malaria cases and controls are presented in Table 1 of the RTS,S/AS01 case-control study analysis report (37), also found in Annex 3.

⁷ Replacement cards are those provided if a child's original HBR has been lost or damaged.

Table 2. Characteristics of severe malaria cases and controls (37)

Variable	Controls	Cases
Number recruited	6151	1546
Number (%) with a vaccine record (HBR or clinic register)	5698 (93%)	1370 (89%)
Number excluding replacement HBRs	5251	1277
Number in matched sets that were retained	4736	1271
Gender		
Boys	2322 (49%)	715 (56%)
Girls	2404 (51%)	556 (44%)
Missing	10 (<1%)	0 (0%)
Source of documented vaccine history		
HBR at home visit	4172 (88%)	896 (70%)
HBR in hospital	0 (0%)	233 (18%)
Clinic register	564 (12%)	142 (11%)
RTS,S/AS01 doses received		
0	1017 (22%)	341 (27%)
1	355 (8%)	138 (11%)
2	434 (9%)	139 (11%)
3	2025 (43%)	470 (37%)
4	905 (19%)	183 (14%)
Mean age, months	24.8	24.7
Caregiver's household wealth ranking		
Low	1584 (33%)	468 (37%)
Middle	1547 (33%)	443 (35%)
High	1605 (34%)	360 (28%)
Caregiver's highest level of education		
None or informal	231 (5%)	80 (6%)
Primary	2989 (63%)	890 (70%)
Secondary	1244 (26%)	257 (20%)
Tertiary	271 (6%)	44 (4%)
Missing	1 (<1%)	0 (0%)
ITN use, at the time of the home visit		
No	515 (11%)	183 (14%)
Yes	4213 (89%)	1065 (84%)
Missing	8 (<1%)	23 (2%)

4.2.1 Effectiveness of three doses against severe malaria

In the adjusted analysis, the **cumulative effectiveness** against severe malaria in children who received three doses of RTS,S/AS01 was 56% (95% CI: 40–67%) during the period until the age scheduled for the fourth dose (an interval of up to 14.5 months), compared to children who did not receive RTS,S/AS01 (Table 3). Among children who received three doses of RTS,S/AS01 but did not go on to receive the fourth dose, the effectiveness against severe malaria declined to 35% (95% CI: 15–50%) during the period from the age scheduled for the fourth dose onwards (37).

Adjustments for covariates made small changes to the odds ratio (OR) for the effects of RTS,S/AS01

vaccination, suggesting that close neighbourhood matching accounted for the effects of socioeconomic status and education, which are often associated with malaria risk.

Table 3. Incremental and cumulative effectiveness of one, two and three doses of RTS,S/AS01 against severe malaria during the period from 0.5 months after receipt of the dose up to the age scheduled for the fourth dose

	Crude OR (95% CI)	Crude OR ^a (95% CI)	Adjusted OR ^b (95% CI)	% effectiveness (95% CI)
The period from 0.5 months after the dose until the age scheduled for the fourth dose:				
RTS,S/AS01 dose number	Incremental effect of each dose			
0	1	1	1	
1	1.22 (0.88–1.71)	1.26 (0.89–1.77)	1.24 (0.88–1.76)	-24% (-76–12%)
2	0.62 (0.43–0.89)	0.62 (0.42–0.90)	0.64 (0.44–0.93)	36% (7–56%)
3	0.56 (0.40–0.78)	0.56 (0.40–0.78)	0.56 (0.40–0.78)	44% (22–60%)
Number of doses	Cumulative effect			
0	1 (Reference)	1 (Reference)	1 (Reference)	
1	1.22 (0.88–1.71)	1.26 (0.89–1.77)	1.24 (0.88–1.76)	-24% (-76–12%)
2	0.75 (0.53–1.07)	0.78 (0.54–1.11)	0.79 (0.55–1.14)	21% (-14–45%)
3	0.42 (0.31–0.56)	0.43 (0.32–0.59)	0.44 (0.33–0.60)	56% (40–67%)

^a crude OR on the subset non-missing for covariates

^b adjusted for child sex, ITN use reported at home visit, caregiver highest level of education, household wealth ranking

Compared to children who did not receive RTS,S/AS01, those who received only three doses had sustained protection against severe malaria during each time interval following receipt of the third dose (Fig. 10): 0.5 up to six months: 56% (95% CI: 35–71%); six up to 18 months: 37% (95% CI: 15–53%); and 18 months or more: 41% (95% CI: 14–59%). Of particular note, the period beginning 18 months after the third dose was the period when an apparent rebound effect was observed in the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial (negative vaccine efficacy with respect to severe malaria) among children who received only three doses. In this study, no rebound was observed, with evidence of sustained effectiveness beyond 18 months after receipt of the third dose (median of 24 months). Section 4.3.1 provides more information on the assessment of rebound of severe malaria cases.

More detailed tables on the severe malaria results are included in the case control study report (37), and also within Annex 3.

Fig. 10. Effectiveness of three doses of RTS,S/AS01 against severe malaria based on the time since receipt of the third dose (with 95% CIs) (37)

Time periods after receiving third dose: 0.5 up to six months after (**0.5–6m**); six up to 18 months after (**6–18m**); and 18 months or more after (**18m+**).

4.2.2 Effectiveness of four doses against severe malaria, and the incremental effectiveness of the fourth dose in children from the scheduled age to receive it

In the adjusted analysis, the **cumulative effectiveness** of four doses of RTS,S/AS01 against severe malaria (compared to unvaccinated children) was 54% (95% CI: 39–66%) (Table 4). Most of the cases in this analysis were 2-4 years old; among the controls, the majority (92%) had received the fourth dose in the previous two years (37).

Regarding **incremental effectiveness**, the fourth dose provides a substantial additional 30% (95% CI: 9–45%) protection against severe malaria (relative reduction in incidence) compared to three doses. Four doses of RTS,S/AS01 provided protection for at least 18 months following receipt of the fourth dose (Fig. 11). The corresponding vaccine efficacies for the time interval since receipt of the fourth dose were: 0.5 up to six months (0.5–6m): 67% (95% CI: 43–81%); six up to 18 months (6–18m): 55% (95% CI: 31–71%); and 18 months or more (18+m): 18% (95% CI: -50–55%). There were limited data for the period beyond 18 months after receiving the fourth dose; although there was no evidence of continued protection during this period, the CI was wide.

Adjustments for other covariates made small changes to the OR for the effects of RTS,S/AS01 vaccination, suggesting that close neighbourhood matching accounted for the effects of socioeconomic status and education, which are often strongly associated with malaria risk.

Table 4. Effectiveness of four doses, and incremental effectiveness of the fourth dose against severe malaria (cases age-eligible to have received the fourth dose) (37)

	Crude OR (95% CI)	Crude OR ^a (95% CI)	Adjusted OR ^b (95% CI)	% effectiveness (95% CI)
The period from the age scheduled for the fourth dose ^c onwards:				
RTS,S/AS01 dose number	Incremental effect of each dose			
0	1	1	1	
1	0.99 (0.64–1.53)	0.92 (0.59–1.43)	0.95 (0.61–1.49)	5% (-49–39%)
2	1.27 (0.76–2.13)	1.34 (0.80–2.26)	1.32 (0.78–2.24)	-32% (-124–22%)
3	0.50 (0.34–0.73)	0.50 (0.34–0.74)	0.51 (0.35–0.76)	49% (24–65%)
4	0.66 (0.52–0.85)	0.66 (0.52–0.85)	0.70 (0.55–0.91)	30% (9–45%)
Number of doses	Cumulative effect			
0	1 (Reference)	1 (Reference)	1 (Reference)	
1	0.99 (0.64–1.53)	0.92 (0.59–1.43)	0.95 (0.61–1.49)	5% (-49–39%)
2	1.26 (0.85–1.88)	1.24 (0.83–1.85)	1.26 (0.84–1.90)	-26% (-90–16%)
3	0.63 (0.48–0.82)	0.65 (0.48–0.81)	0.65 (0.50–0.85)	35% (15–50%)
4	0.42 (0.32–0.55)	0.41 (0.31–0.55)	0.46 (0.34–0.61)	54% (39–66%)

^a crude OR on the subset non-missing for covariates

^b adjusted for child sex, ITN use reported at home visit, caregiver highest level of education, household wealth ranking

^c Age scheduled for the fourth dose depended on the country's four-dose malaria vaccine schedule: at 22 months of age in Malawi (15 months after third dose); at 24 months of age in Ghana (15 months after third dose) until January 2023, when the fourth dose shifted to 18 months of age (nine months after third dose); and at 24 months of age in Kenya (15 months after third dose).

More detailed tables on the severe malaria results are included in the case control study report (37), and also within Annex 3.

Fig. 11. Effectiveness of four doses of RTS,S/AS01 against severe malaria based on time since the fourth dose (37)

Time periods after receiving the fourth dose: 0.5 up to six months after (**0.5–6m**); six up to 18 months after (**6–18m**); and 18 months or more after (**18m+**).

4.2.3 Effectiveness against cerebral malaria

A total of 182 cases of cerebral malaria and 727 controls were recruited. Documented vaccine history was available for 80% (146/182) of cases and 74% (539/727) of controls. Among these, about 64% (94/146) of cases and 79% (426/539) of controls had received one or more doses of RTS,S/AS01.

Compared to receiving no doses of RTS,S/AS01, receiving one or more doses of RTS,S/AS01 was associated with an average protective effectiveness of 61% (95% CI: 35–76%) against cerebral malaria (Table 5).

Table 5. ORs for the association of RTS,S/AS01 with cerebral malaria

RTS,S/AS01 doses received	Crude OR (95% CI)	Crude OR ^a (95% CI)	Adjusted OR ^b (95% CI)	% effectiveness (95% CI)
0 doses	1 (Reference)	1 (Reference)	1 (Reference)	
Any dose (one, two, three, or four)	0.35 (0.22–0.56)	0.35 (0.21–0.56)	0.39 (0.24–0.65)	61% (35–76%)

^a crude OR on the subset non-missing for covariates

^b adjusted for child sex, ITN use reported at home visit, caregiver highest level of education, household wealth ranking

Average vaccine effectiveness of three doses against cerebral malaria was 73% (95% CI: 18–91%) during the period before the age scheduled for the fourth dose, and 53% (95%CI: 10–76%) after this time in children who did not receive the fourth dose; effectiveness of four doses was 74% (95% CI: 43–88%).

However, tests of interaction did not show evidence that effectiveness against cerebral malaria differed from other forms of severe malaria, with respect to three or four doses of RTS,S/AS01.

More detailed tables on the cerebral malaria results are included in the case control study report (37), and also within Annex 3.

4.2.4 Overall assessment of three- versus four-dose schedule effectiveness

- Compared to the protection from three doses of RTS,S/AS01 vaccine, the fourth dose provided an incremental effectiveness against severe malaria of **30%** (95% CI: 9–45%).
- Before the scheduled age when the fourth dose was due, receipt of three doses of RTS,S/AS01 was associated with protection of **56%** (95% CI: 40–67%) against severe malaria. If children missed the fourth dose, there was evidence of continued protection (**35%**; 95% CI: 15–50%). For children who received the fourth dose, the protection was sustained at least 18 months after receipt of the fourth dose, with average protection of 54% (95% CI: 39–66%).
- Average vaccine effectiveness of three doses against cerebral malaria was 73% (95% CI: 18–91%) during the period before the age scheduled for the fourth dose, and 53% (95%CI: 10–76%) after this time in children who did not receive the fourth dose; effectiveness of four doses was 74% (95% CI: 43–88%). However, tests of interaction did not show evidence that RTS,S/AS01 effectiveness against cerebral malaria differed from other forms of severe malaria, with respect to three or four doses.
- The results for severe malaria from the RTS,S/AS01 case–control study, including the sustained duration of protection, are broadly consistent with the vaccine efficacy against **clinical malaria** measured in the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial in the trial sites with low and moderate transmission. The case–control findings are also broadly consistent with the impact observed against **severe malaria** in the cluster-randomized MVIP pilot evaluations, taking into account the levels of coverage of three and four doses in the MVIP (2019–2023).

4.3 RTS,S/AS01 case–control study: safety

In terms of safety, the case–control study was undertaken to assess evidence for a severe malaria rebound effect in children who received only three doses, and to estimate associations with the three safety signals that were identified in the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial. These three safety signals were rigorously evaluated through the MVIP and ultimately no evidence of association with the vaccine was found, supporting the conclusion that these were chance findings in the Phase 3 trial (3).

4.3.1 Rebound

The case–control study found no rebound effect for the risk of severe malaria. A rebound effect would have been demonstrated by a negative measure of vaccine effectiveness during the period from approximately 18 months after the third dose in children who did not receive a fourth malaria vaccine dose. In contrast, positive vaccine effectiveness was observed (41%; 95% CI: 14–59%) beyond 18 months after the third dose in children who did not receive a fourth dose (Fig. 10; section 4.2.1). In the analysis that was restricted to the period 18 months or more after the third dose, the cases were aged approximately 2–4 years. Of the controls who had received three doses, the majority (78%) had received the third dose during the previous 12 to 36 months. Of the children who did not receive the fourth vaccine dose, Fig. 12 shows the months since receipt of the third dose among severe malaria cases (A) and controls (B) from the time when children were due for the fourth dose.

Fig. 12. Of the children who did not receive the fourth vaccine dose, months since receipt of the third dose among severe malaria cases (A) and controls (B) from the time when children were due for the fourth dose

Among discordant matched sets included in analyses of the effectiveness of three doses

4.3.2 Safety

There was no evidence that RTS,S/AS01 vaccination (any dose) was associated with the three safety signals observed in the Phase 3 trial but not found after rigorous investigation in the MVIP. The case–control study also showed no excess risk of meningitis (adjusted OR: 0.96; 95% CI: 0.38–2.40) or of cerebral malaria (adjusted OR: 0.39; 95% CI: 0.24–0.65). There was no evidence of an increased risk of mortality when comparing boys and girls who received any dose of the RTS,S/AS01 vaccine: The ORs were 0.58 (95% CI: 0.46–0.74) among boys and 0.68 (95% CI: 0.52–0.89) for girls. The interaction parameter (relative OR girls:boys) was 1.16 (95% CI: 0.82–1.63; $p=0.397$); when adjusted for caregiver education, household wealth ranking, gender, and receipt of first and second dose of the measles vaccine, it was 1.24 (95%CI: 0.87–1.77; $p=0.296$).

Details on the safety outcomes are presented in the RTS,S/AS01 case–control study analysis report (37), also found in Annex 3.

4.3.3 RTS,S/AS01 case–control study overall assessment of safety

The RTS,S/AS01 MVIP DSMB monitored the case–control study and provided recommendations to the study team during the conduct of the study and after review of the preliminary analysis. The DSMB concluded that there was no evidence of the safety signals that were seen in the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial (2009–2014). The following were the MVIP DSMB’s conclusions:

- **Meningitis:** The case–control study showed no increased risk of meningitis in children who received the RTS,S/AS01 vaccine compared to unvaccinated children.
- **Cerebral malaria:** The results showed no evidence of increased risk of cerebral malaria; the analysis indicates a protective effect of RTS,S/AS01 against cerebral malaria.
- **Severe malaria rebound:** The data did not show evidence of severe malaria rebound in children

who received three doses but failed to receive a fourth dose, compared to unvaccinated children. The analysis shows protection from three doses of RTS,S/AS01. Protection farther out from when the third dose was received may decrease relative to natural immunity (controls), but at no time point presented was there an increased risk of severe malaria among vaccinated children relative to controls.

- **Imbalance in effectiveness of RTS,S/AS01 by gender, with respect to sex-specific mortality:** There was no evidence that the effectiveness of RTS,S/AS01 against all-cause mortality differed between girls and boys.

Following review of the case–control study results, the SAGE/MPAG Working Group on Malaria Vaccines agreed with the RTS,S/AS01 MVIP DSMB’s conclusions.

5. Considerations on three-dose versus four-dose schedule for R21/Matrix-M

There are no data comparing the efficacy or effectiveness of three doses versus four doses of the R21/Matrix-M vaccine. The R21/Matrix-M vaccine and the RTS,S/AS01 are similar in their vaccine construct, antigenic target and mechanism of action. The high vaccine efficacy against clinical malaria observed for R21/Matrix-M in the Phase 3 clinical trial in the 12 months following the third dose is similar to that of RTS,S/AS01.

In the R21/Matrix-M Phase 3 trial, there were relatively few cases of severe malaria, malaria hospitalizations or all-cause mortality, resulting in insufficient power to estimate vaccine efficacy against these end-points. However, given the efficacy against clinical malaria, the efficacy of R21/Matrix-M against severe malaria is expected to be high. In addition, the R21/Matrix-M Phase 3 clinical trial did not evaluate vaccine efficacy in high perennial transmission settings. However, given its similarity to RTS,S/AS01, it is reasonable to assume that R21/Matrix-M will also be efficacious in all malaria endemicities. Post-licensure studies are recommended to evaluate the public health impact of R21/Matrix-M in different epidemiological settings. A Phase 4 case–control study has been proposed to further evaluate the effectiveness of R21/Matrix-M against severe malaria and mortality and against clinical malaria in high perennial transmission areas.

In the R21/Matrix-M Phase 3 trial sites evaluating age-based vaccination, vaccine efficacy against clinical malaria waned minimally in the 12 months after receiving the third dose (before receiving the fourth dose). Vaccine efficacy was 72% (95% CI: 58–81%) in the first six months after the third dose, decreasing to 62% (95% CI: 52–70%) in the second six months after the third dose. All children in the trial received a fourth dose one year after the third dose, so there are no data on the duration of protection of three doses of R21/Matrix-M after 12 months.

6. Contextual and implementation considerations for a three-dose versus four-dose schedule

This section addresses the contextual and implementation considerations of a three-dose versus four-dose schedule, complementing the assessment of benefits and risks in the evidence-to-recommendation framework. The focus is on age-based delivery of a three- or four-dose schedule in areas of perennial malaria transmission, excluding seasonal or hybrid delivery approaches, which are relevant options mainly in highly seasonal settings.

The following considerations are discussed:

- resource use
- feasibility
- values, preferences and acceptability
- equity.

6.1 Resource use

A three-dose schedule would require fewer resources compared to a four-dose schedule however, the extent of resource savings depends on the country context and the perspective taken—whether from the standpoint of the government or the caregiver. Transitioning from a four-dose to a three-dose schedule could, in theory, yield up to a 25% cost reduction – assuming no drop-out between doses – from a vaccine product cost perspective, as well as a 25% reduction in the recurrent delivery costs per dose. The actual cost savings will be country-specific and will depend, among other factors, on the drop-out rates between the third and fourth doses.

Any potential government savings from the vaccine programme would need to be weighed against the potential increase in diagnosis and treatment costs for malaria cases, including severe malaria cases, that would occur if the fourth dose was not administered. Similarly, any caregiver cost savings – such as reduced time and travel for vaccination – would need to be weighed against potential increases in out-of-pocket expenses for malaria treatment, transportation and lost income from time away from daily activities.

Among countries that are already implementing a four-dose schedule, additional one-time costs would be incurred to support a switch to a three-dose schedule, including updated information, education and communication materials, recording and reporting tools, guidance and training refreshers for health workers, as well as activities related to planning and coordination (e.g. committee and subcommittee meetings) and stakeholder engagement (e.g. briefings, community sensitization).

6.1.1 Vaccine cost

The two malaria vaccines that are recommended and prequalified by WHO are currently made available via procurement by UNICEF at a price of US\$ 3.90 per dose for R21/Matrix-M (two-dose vial presentation, liquid) and EUR 9.30 per dose for RTS,S/AS01 (two-dose vial presentation, lyophilized) (38). This translates into a vaccine product cost of approximately US\$ 15.60 to US\$ 43.10 per child for a complete four-dose schedule (not considering potential wastage) and of approximately US\$ 11.70 to US\$ 32.40 per child for a complete three-dose schedule – a cost savings of 25%.

The cost of the malaria vaccine is currently higher than other Gavi-supported vaccines. This is not unexpected, given that it is a relatively new vaccine with a limited supplier base and a recently launched Gavi support programme. Both demand and supply volumes are still ramping up and have not yet reached a steady-state level where larger economies of scale – and corresponding cost reductions – can be

realized. Gavi and UNICEF have a strong track record of shaping vaccine markets to achieve healthier market dynamics, including reduced vaccine prices over time, while ensuring supply security. UNICEF expects weighted average malaria vaccine prices per dose to decrease over time (39). At the Global Summit on 25 June 2025 to replenish Gavi's finances for the next strategic period (2026–2030), both malaria vaccine manufacturers committed to future price reductions: GSK and Bharat Biotech announced that the price of the RTS,S/AS01 vaccine would be reduced by more than half, progressively, to less than US\$ 5 per dose by 2028 (40). Serum Institute of India committed to substantially lowering the price of the R21/Matrix-M vaccine during Gavi's next strategic period, potentially saving Gavi and implementing countries over US\$ 100 million, depending on final approvals and procurement volumes (23).

If Gavi maintains its current guidelines for malaria vaccine support, which allows eligible countries to request vaccine assistance for a four- or five-dose schedule to cover areas representing up to 85% of the total target population in moderate and high malaria transmission settings, Gavi projects a need for approximately US\$ 1127 million for the malaria vaccine programme from 2026 to 2030 (41). This would account for 9.5% of Gavi's total projected expenditures during that period, making the malaria vaccine the most expensive single vaccine programme.

To make the new malaria vaccine more affordable for eligible countries, in December 2022, Gavi approved an exceptional and time-limited co-financing modality for malaria vaccines. Under the revised policy, the lowest income countries contribute US\$ 0.20 per dose, while countries in the accelerated transition phase will co-finance an increasing proportion of the price over a period of eight years up to full self-financing.

From a vaccine product cost perspective, transitioning from a four-dose to a three-dose schedule could, in theory, yield up to a 25% cost reduction – assuming no drop-out between doses. However, the actual savings are likely to be lower and will vary depending on drop-out rates and country context. For countries in Gavi's two lowest co-financing groups, any relative cost savings would be shared proportionally between Gavi and the country. In contrast, for countries in the accelerated transition co-financing group, the share of savings accruing to the country would increase progressively over time.

6.1.2 Cost of delivery

Most of the initial introduction and set-up costs – such as planning, training, development of communication and social mobilization materials, and revision of recording tools – are generally not influenced by the number of doses in the immunization schedule. An important exception is the potential cost of expanding cold chain capacity at various levels of the health system, which might be needed in some countries. The RTS,S/AS01 vaccine requires 9.92 cm³ per dose (in secondary packaging), while R21/Matrix-M requires 7.03 cm³ per dose. Depending on a country's available cold chain capacity prior to introduction, additional equipment may be needed to accommodate a four-dose schedule compared to a three-dose schedule. For the countries that have already implemented a four-dose schedule, the switch to a three-dose schedule would incur additional one-time costs, including updated information, education communication materials, recording and reporting tools, guidance and training refreshers for health workers, as well as activities related to planning and coordination (e.g. committee and subcommittee meetings) and stakeholder engagement (e.g. briefings, community sensitization, etc.).

A retrospective cost of delivery study evaluated the cost of phased subnational introduction and delivery of the RTS,S/AS01 malaria vaccine in each of the pilot countries (Ghana, Kenya and Malawi) using a four-dose age-based schedule (year-round delivery with vaccine administration based on the child's age)(42). The reported cost estimates were based on target populations and coverage levels from administrative data in the three pilot countries; the following coverage levels in Ghana, Kenya, and Malawi were used for the first dose: 72%, 75%, 93%, respectively; for the second dose: 66%, 73%, 84%; for the third dose: 58%, 75%, 80%; and for the fourth dose 46%, 57%, 54% after approximately one year of fourth dose

administration.

The cost of delivery study estimated the incremental financial costs (actual financial outlays) and economic costs (financial costs plus opportunity cost of existing resources including labour) per dose for vaccine introduction and delivery from a provider perspective (e.g. government). Excluding the cost of vaccines, immunization supplies and procurement add-on costs, the estimated recurrent cost of delivery per dose ranged from US\$ 0.29 to US\$ 0.86 (financial) and from US\$ 0.59 to US\$ 2.29 (economic). This includes activities such as regular vaccine distribution through the cold chain system from national stores down to health facilities, service delivery in routine static clinics and outreach activities, defaulter tracing, communication and public education, and supportive supervision. Recurrent costs exclude the initial set-up costs related to RTS,S/AS01 MVIP introduction and delivery and are expected to be more representative of the programme costs in the long run.

The differential estimates for the delivery of the third and fourth doses reported in the study are not used here due to limitations in the underlying data (at the time of analysis, fewer than 40% of children who had received the first three doses were eligible for the fourth dose, resulting in an upward bias in the estimated cost per dose and cost per fully immunized child for four doses, as the denominator did not yet reflect the full eligible population). No empirical evidence was retrieved indicating whether the operational cost of delivering the fourth dose is higher than that of any of the first three doses. It could be hypothesized that unit costs of the fourth dose may be higher if countries implement increased social mobilization or defaulter tracing systems, or conduct catch-up activities – particularly in the second year of life – to reach children who missed earlier doses. However, since such activities typically benefit multiple antigens, it is challenging to attribute a specific incremental cost to the malaria vaccine alone.

As for vaccine costs, assuming equal unit costs of delivery across all doses with no drop-out, shifting from a four-dose to a three-dose schedule could, in theory, yield up to a 25% reduction of delivery costs. However, the actual savings are likely to be lower and will vary depending on drop-out rates and country context.

6.2 Feasibility

The current WHO recommendation states that malaria vaccines should be provided to children in a four-dose schedule from around 5 months of age. The first three doses are administered to children within their first year of life, with a minimum interval of four weeks between each dose. The fourth dose is given in the second year of life or, in some countries, at the beginning of the third year. WHO recommends scheduling the fourth dose 6–18 months after the third dose to prolong protection.

The malaria vaccine schedule adopted by the 22 countries that have introduced the vaccine as of 1 September 2025 is shown in Fig. 3. All countries have chosen to provide the first three doses between 5 and 9 months of age. This implies at least one new immunization contact (for some countries up to three) in the first year of life. The fourth dose is typically administered during an existing vaccination visit in the second year of life, for example for the second dose of measles-containing vaccine (MCV-2) or meningococcal vaccine – most often at 15, 16 or 18 months of age, depending on the country context. To date, six countries have chosen a new vaccination touchpoint for the fourth dose: Kenya (24 months) and Malawi (22 months) due to historical WHO guidance (see below); Benin, Central African Republic and South Sudan because it is the country's first vaccine provided in the second year of life; and Cameroon for other contextual reasons.

The operational feasibility of implementing a malaria vaccine with a four-dose schedule has been evaluated through the MVIP, with the ministries of health in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi delivering the RTS,S/AS01 malaria vaccine in selected areas through their national immunization programmes since

2019. In 2016, when the pilot countries started planning implementation, WHO recommended an interval of 15–18 months between the third and fourth doses. This interval was later revised to 6–18 months and countries were encouraged to align the fourth dose with other vaccines administered in the second year of life. Ghana and Kenya chose a schedule of 6, 7, 9 and 24 months; this schedule implied three new immunization contacts, with the visit at 9 months of age coinciding with administration of the first dose of measles-rubella vaccine. Malawi chose a schedule of 5, 6, 7 and 22 months, implying four new immunization contacts. Overall, the MVIP demonstrated high community demand for the malaria vaccine, strong health worker acceptability, and the capacity of countries to effectively deliver the vaccine through the childhood immunization platform, despite the novel four-dose schedule.

Malaria vaccine coverage estimates in the MVIP countries are available from two sources: independent household surveys and administrative data reported through the routine health information system.

6.2.1 Household survey results

In each country, household surveys were conducted at baseline (before or shortly after malaria vaccine introduction), at approximately 18 months (midline), and again around 30 months post-introduction (endline). These surveys aimed to estimate, among other indicators, coverage of the malaria vaccine and other childhood vaccines, as well as to monitor ITN use and care-seeking behaviour for fever (14).⁸

In sum, relatively high levels of third dose coverage (62–67%) were achieved in all countries soon after introduction (midline household survey, Fig. 13) (14). There was an improvement in third dose coverage between the midline and endline surveys (an interval of about 16 months). Coverage of the fourth dose was lower in all countries: at 33–34% in Malawi and Kenya, and 53% in Ghana. Missed opportunities for malaria vaccination were evident from the higher coverage achieved with the first dose of measles-containing vaccine (MCV-1) scheduled at 9 months of age than with the first dose of malaria vaccine. There was similar coverage in each country in the first year of life, with slightly lower uptake in Malawi. Coverage of MCV-2 and coverage of the fourth dose of malaria vaccine were higher in Ghana than in the other countries.

⁸ Mwapasa V, Asante, KP, Milligan P, Akech S, Oduro A, Mathanga D, et al. The impact of introducing the RTS,S/AS01E malaria vaccine delivered through routine immunisation programmes on mortality in young children: 46-month evaluation of cluster-randomised deployment of the vaccine in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi. Not yet published (as of 1 September 2025).

Fig. 13. Coverage of four doses of RTS,S/AS01 malaria vaccine (RTS,S 1–4), Penta-3, MCV-1 and MCV-2 in implementation areas of MVP countries, based on household surveys (14)

HHS: household survey

6.2.2 Administrative data reports

Annual coverage estimates for 2020 to 2024 based on administrative data from the routine health information system are shown in Fig. 14 (43). From the start of vaccination in pilot countries (2019) through the end of 2024, over 9.5 million doses of the malaria vaccine were administered across Ghana, Kenya and Malawi; more than 3 million children received at least one dose, and over 1.3 children completed the four-dose schedule. While variation in performance was observed across and within the three countries, according to administrative data, by the end of 2024, all three countries had reached approximately 80% of their target populations with the first dose and at least 77% with the third dose (Fig. 14). The drop-out between the first and third doses was small in Ghana and Kenya (< 5% in 2024), but slightly more important in Malawi (12% in 2024). In all three countries, drop-out rates decreased over time. Of note, the global coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic, natural disasters and occasional health worker strikes disrupted stocks and/or access to vaccines at various time points in each of the three countries, but uptake in all countries returned to previous levels once the disruptions had been resolved, demonstrating the resilience of the immunization programmes, the high demand for the malaria vaccine from the community, and acceptability by health workers.

Fig. 14. Annual immunization coverage estimates for the first, third and fourth doses of malaria vaccine (RTS,S-1, -3, -4), Penta-3, MCV-1 and MCV-2 in initial implementing areas of MVIP countries, 2020–2024, based on routine administrative data reports

Note: Originally scheduled at 24 months of age, the schedule for the fourth dose of malaria vaccine in Ghana was changed to 18 months of age from February 2023.

Uptake of the fourth dose has been lower. Although coverage of the fourth dose has increased gradually over time, it has hovered around 50% over the last two years (2023–2024) in Kenya and Malawi. A similar trend of lower coverage has been observed for other vaccines administered in the second year of a child's life; for instance, the second doses of measles-rubella vaccine administered at 15 months in Malawi and

18 months in Kenya have coverage levels of 63% and 66%, respectively. This points to general (rather than vaccine-specific) challenges with reaching children at an older age (43).

Large increases in uptake were noted in Ghana after the immunization schedule was changed in early 2023 to administer the fourth dose at 18 months of age rather than at 24 months of age. With this change, the dose fell within the second-year-of-life platform and coincided with administration of the meningococcal A vaccine, MCV-2, and provision of ITNs. Fourth dose coverage increased almost immediately – from 53% in 2022 to 83% in 2023 – and has since aligned more closely with MCV-2 coverage.

Importantly, the significant impact observed during the MVIP – i.e. a 13% (95% CI: 3–23%) vaccine-attributable reduction in all-cause mortality (excluding injury) and 22% (95% CI: 4–37%) reduction in severe malaria hospitalizations in children age-eligible for vaccination⁹ – took place during a period of vaccine scale-up when approximately 71% (range across the three countries 63–75%) of age-eligible children had received at least three vaccine doses and only 40% (range 33–53%) had received four doses (14).

In sum, a four-dose schedule is feasible to implement and delivers substantial health impact, even with suboptimal levels of fourth dose coverage.

It is currently too early to conduct a systematic assessment of the uptake of the fourth dose in countries that introduced malaria vaccines in early 2024, as the first children eligible for this dose were expected to return only in Q1–Q2 2025.

Although a three-dose schedule has not been implemented programmatically outside of clinical trials, it is reasonable to assume that if the MVIP countries had implemented a three-dose schedule, they would have achieved coverage levels similar to those observed for the third dose within the four-dose schedule (i.e. around 80%) since the timing of the first three doses is identical in both schedules. Completing a three-dose schedule within the first year of life would be more achievable for individual children than completing a four-dose schedule that extends into the second or third year of life. In addition, a three-dose schedule is certain to cost less than a four-dose schedule and is likely to simplify logistics (e.g. less cold chain volume required), delivery (e.g. health worker time savings), and communication with caregivers and communities.

6.2.3 Assessment and expert opinions: feasibility

Expert opinions were sought from current and former national immunization and malaria programme managers in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi, reflecting their personal views rather than official government positions.

The consulted experts confirmed that a four-dose schedule is feasible to implement. A primary challenge lies in the cost, particularly for countries in Gavi’s accelerated transition phase (as is the case for Ghana and Kenya in 2025); in this phase, co-financing obligations increase over time as a share of the vaccine price, rather than being fixed per dose. However, experts indicated that this challenge may be overcome with reductions in vaccine product cost over time (which are expected due to higher volumes procured over time and successful market-shaping efforts by Gavi or a product switch by some countries). Both Ghana and Kenya have received exceptional Gavi approval to switch from RTS,S/AS01 to R21/Matrix-M to

⁹ Mwapasa V, Asante, KP, Milligan P, Akech S, Oduro A, Mathanga D, et al. The impact of introducing the RTS,S/AS01E malaria vaccine delivered through routine immunisation programmes on mortality in young children: 46-month evaluation of cluster-randomised deployment of the vaccine in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi. Not yet published (as of 1 September 2025).

help ease the financial burden for the countries.

Some respondents emphasized that the fourth dose has strengthened linkages with other second-year-of-life interventions. Whether scheduled at the same time as other antigens and health services (e.g. in Ghana, with meningococcal A vaccine, MCV-2, vitamin A and ITN provision at 18 months of age) or several months later (e.g. in Kenya, where the fourth dose is scheduled at a new visit at 24 months), there have been opportunities to reinforce the second-year-of-life delivery platform, improving uptake over time. Good uptake (> 80%) was achieved with the fourth dose of malaria vaccine in Ghana after the schedule was aligned with other antigens and health services given at 18 months of age.

Consulted experts cautioned that for countries that have already started implementing a four-dose schedule (21 countries, as of 1 September 2025), switching to a three-dose schedule would pose significant challenges. Beyond the financial and operational implications of a switch, such a change could undermine trust in immunization programmes and affect acceptability. Current ministry of health messaging emphasizes the need for four doses for optimal protection, and revising this to promote a less effective three-dose schedule could affect programme credibility and health worker and community acceptance (see section 6.3.3).

As such, if a three-dose schedule is recommended by WHO as an option, it may be launched more easily in areas where the vaccine has yet to be introduced. However, consulted national immunization programme managers emphasized that implementing different schedules across the country (three doses in some areas, four doses in others) would not be operationally feasible. A uniform national schedule is preferable to ensure consistency and ease of incorporation into the childhood immunization schedule, accommodate population and health worker mobility and changing epidemiology, and support streamlined training, data recording and reporting systems. One former malaria control manager indicated that while it was important to maintain a four-dose schedule in moderate and high transmission areas, a three-dose schedule could potentially be proposed as an option to caregivers of children living in low transmission urban areas where access to treatment is more readily available.

6.3 Values, preferences and acceptability

To the Working Group's knowledge, there is no direct evidence or published study assessing the values and preferences of the target population or the acceptability among key stakeholders of a three-dose versus four-dose malaria vaccine schedule. This section summarizes evidence from the MVIP household surveys and health utilization study related to the third and fourth doses; vaccine schedule optimization examples from other antigens, although there is no experience of switching to a vaccine schedule with less protection; and expert opinions from current or former immunization and malaria control programme managers.

6.3.1 Evidence from the MVIP

The MVIP generated evidence on the acceptability of a four-dose malaria vaccine schedule through a series of cross-sectional household surveys, post-introduction evaluations and qualitative health utilization studies. Malaria vaccine coverage results are presented in section 6.1.

Other key findings from the household surveys include the following:¹⁰

- **Impact on childhood vaccination coverage:** In all countries, surveys found no impact of RTS,S/AS01 introduction on the uptake of other childhood vaccines. Coverage of Penta-3 remained high – over 90% – in all three countries (see Fig. 13). Similarly, coverage of the first dose

¹⁰ Further details can be found in the RTS,S/AS01 full evidence report (3).

of measles-rubella vaccine remained over 85% in all three countries. Administration of the malaria vaccine as part of the immunization programmes continued despite the challenges and effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. The ability of the national immunization programmes to maintain or improve upon performance, and to quickly recover from COVID-19-related and other disruptions, is a testament to their resilience. It also demonstrates the demand for the vaccine by caregivers and the acceptance by health workers who provide the vaccine.

- **Use of malaria prevention and control:** In all countries, surveys found no impact on the use of ITNs among children following introduction of the malaria vaccine and no impact on health-seeking behaviour. ITN use among children aged 5–48 months was over 60% in Ghana, over 80% in Malawi, and over 90% in Kenya, with no significant differences between children living in vaccine implementing and neighbouring comparison areas or over time. In each country, over 60% had sought advice or treatment for fever in the previous two weeks; of those who sought treatment, there was no impact on the use of malaria diagnostic testing or receipt of antimalarials for treatment. Results were comparable between baseline and endline surveys in Ghana, Malawi and Kenya, and between implementation and comparison areas.
- **Impact of RTS,S/AS01 on other child health activities or indices:** Overall, there was no impact on the uptake of vitamin A or anthelmintics (deworming).

The health utilization study, a qualitative longitudinal component of the MVIP, explored health provider and primary caregiver perceptions of the RTS,S/AS01 malaria vaccine, examined its influence on malaria treatment-seeking and other preventive behaviours, and assessed the acceptability and feasibility of delivering the four-dose schedule (44). Positive attitudes and trust in the malaria vaccine among primary caregivers increased substantially over time, driven mainly by the perception of the health benefits of the vaccine in their own children and reinforced by community norms and perceived shared experiences of reduced malaria cases among children in the broader community. While there were early concerns about safety, those were replaced by widespread perception that adverse events following immunization were normal and similar to other vaccines. Primary caregivers and health workers perceived that the vaccine resulted in less frequent and less severe malaria (resulting in fewer children reporting to the facilities with malaria). Key concerns among health providers were the operational challenges faced in introducing and delivering the vaccine (e.g. increased workloads, and lack of adequate training and supportive supervision), lack of clarity about missed or delayed vaccination, and lack of community sensitization on key messages.

Overwhelmingly, the impetus to complete the schedule was driven by the perceived vaccine benefits, frequently expressed in comparison to unvaccinated children or previous health status in the vaccinated child. The study explored reasons for non-completion of the schedule among children who had received the first three doses. Alone or in combination, service barriers, competing life demands, imprecise understanding of fourth dose eligibility, and satisfaction with the perceived protection from three malaria vaccine doses often outweighed or precluded the acceptance of the fourth dose. The study suggests that additional community engagement, intensified and clearer communication, and alignment of the fourth dose with existing visits (e.g. MCV-2 at 18 months) may improve acceptability among caregivers. The study did not assess stakeholder or caregiver preferences for a three-dose schedule.

The introduction of the malaria vaccine in a four-dose schedule in 21 countries to date confirms its acceptability among key stakeholders.

6.3.2 Evidence from other vaccines

Some evidence regarding the acceptability of lower dose schedules among stakeholders is available from schedule optimization studies for other vaccines (e.g. HPV vaccine and PCV; see section 2.4 Vaccine schedule modifications); however, the applicability of these findings to malaria vaccination is uncertain, given the comparatively much higher incremental benefit observed with the fourth dose of the malaria vaccine compared to the first three doses.

- In April 2022, when SAGE considered whether to recommend an off-label, permissive one-dose HPV vaccine schedule for use in routine and/or multi-age cohort catch-up strategies as an alternative to the previously recommended two-dose schedule, a small-scale informal survey was conducted among national immunization programmes in low- and middle-income countries with current or planned HPV vaccine programmes (45). The majority of respondents indicated they would consider adopting a one-dose recommendation for multi-age cohorts on programmatic grounds. However, the survey did not specifically explore the acceptability of reducing the routine cohort to a single dose. Notably, SAGE and WHO policy endorsements were cited as important criteria influencing NITAG decision-making. A small-scale study conducted in the United Republic of Tanzania found that most participants entrusted decisions about the number of HPV vaccine doses to health experts (46). When presented with a hypothetical choice, adolescent girls generally preferred fewer doses to avoid the pain of injections. Caregiver views were more varied: While most prioritized whichever schedule was deemed most efficacious, a few associated a higher number of doses with greater protection.
- A study in the Gambia examined the knowledge, attitudes and preferences of infant caregivers and vaccinators regarding the standard three-dose PCV schedule versus an alternative two-dose schedule (47). Both vaccinators and caregivers showed a preference for the alternative PCV schedule, primarily due to the reduced pain and discomfort for children and fewer clinic visits. Vaccinators also noted potential cost savings and emphasized the importance of educating caregivers to support adherence, particularly when multiple injections are required at a single visit. While some vaccinators favoured the standard schedule for its perceived added immunity, overall trust in vaccines and health workers remained high among caregivers, reinforcing confidence in whichever schedule is recommended.

6.3.3 Assessment and expert opinions: values, preferences and acceptability

The consultations with the current and former immunization and malaria programme managers in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi, as referenced above, also sought their expert judgement on values, preferences and acceptability associated with the two options.

The consulted experts indicated that a four-dose schedule was likely more acceptable to the ministry of health, as well as to the target population, because it clearly provided more protection than a three-dose schedule. As reported above, the main barrier that could affect acceptability was the higher cost and related sustainability concerns.

They reported that, for the target population (i.e. caregivers of infants and young children living in malaria-endemic areas), the potential benefits of avoiding the time, logistical efforts and travel costs associated with getting the fourth dose, as well as reduced risk of adverse events from one fewer injection, are very likely outweighed by the risks of lower overall protection against severe malaria and death associated with a three-dose schedule. Since the vaccine is free of charge in most settings, caregivers are unlikely to perceive a reduction of the vaccine product cost as a personal benefit.

There was a strong request from experts from the ministries of health that in the event of a WHO recommendation for a three-dose schedule (as an alternative to a four-dose schedule), implementing countries and their respective NITAGs should have the final decision on which schedule to adopt. Country ownership of schedule choice may be challenging to maintain where external partners provide financial support for malaria vaccine volumes and prioritize cost savings.

Experts stated that acceptability among health workers and caregivers will likely hinge on communication around the rationale for why a fourth dose is no longer provided, or why a three-dose schedule has been recommended. If not well managed, communication around a three-dose schedule could undermine public confidence in vaccination and damage the reputation and credibility of the national immunization programme. It would be challenging to convey that a three-dose schedule offers less protection than a four-dose schedule, especially in countries that have already invested in consistent messaging emphasizing four doses as essential for optimal and sustained protection. Countries that have already introduced a four-dose schedule would need to invest time and resources in planning, activities and materials for stakeholder engagement and community sensitization prior to any schedule switch. One former malaria programme manager expressed deep concern that referencing cost savings as a justification for switching to a three-dose schedule would be unethical.

A four-dose schedule with additional vaccination contacts presents an opportunity to strengthen health systems and deliver complementary interventions that protect child health, particularly during the second year of life. In addition, several countries are leveraging the collaboration and comparative advantages of national immunization and malaria programmes to boost immunization coverage during SMC campaigns, and vaccination visits in turn are being used as platforms to deliver preventive malaria treatments or distribute ITNs.

6.4 Equity

6.4.1 Current state

According to WHO, equity is the absence of unfair, avoidable and remediable differences in health status among groups of people (48). Fairness can be understood through a variety of theoretical perspectives. The vast majority of malaria illness and death occurs in Africa and in children under 5 years of age. Malaria disproportionately affects the poor and those living in rural areas. HIV exposure, HIV infection or chronic malnutrition, all of which frequently overlap geographically with areas of malaria endemicity, are additional risk factors for malaria-associated illness or death (49, 50). Therefore, access to additional malaria prevention through vaccination is expected to increase global health equity. Immunization programmes have frequently been shown to reach higher coverage than is achieved by many existing approaches to malaria control; the potential to reach high coverage with a malaria vaccine could help to reduce inequities in access to malaria control interventions. A 2020 analysis of Demographic and Health Survey and malaria indicator survey data from 20 African countries showed that among the 33 million children who did not use ITNs, 23 million (70%) were reached by childhood immunization programmes (51).

Currently, a significant proportion of eligible children in malaria-endemic countries lack access to malaria vaccines. At the time of WHO's initial recommendation for vaccine use in 2021, severe global supply constraints limited the pace and scale of introductions, leading most countries to adopt a phased, subnational roll-out beginning in geographical areas where the need was greatest. Vaccine supply has increased since late 2023 following the recommendation of a second malaria vaccine and is now sufficient to meet global demand. However, financial constraints – particularly for Gavi, the primary funder, as well as for countries – remain a key barrier to accelerating roll-out. As of August 2025, Gavi offers support to eligible countries for vaccine procurement to cover geographical areas representing up to 85% of eligible

children in moderate and high transmission settings; this leaves the remaining 15% of children without access unless countries can mobilize additional domestic or external resources. Thus far, six countries have been able to extend malaria vaccination to more than 85% of the target population in moderate and high transmission areas, with three of them achieving nationwide scale-up by leveraging domestic resources to close the funding gap. In contrast, the remaining implementing countries currently offer malaria vaccination to between 4% and 85% of at-risk children in moderate and high transmission areas (median of approximately 30%), with the intention for scale-up if funding permits.

6.4.2 Household survey evidence

Evidence from the MVIP endline household surveys shows that similar coverage of three doses of RTS,S/AS01 and of the fourth dose was achieved in girls and boys in each country. However, coverage tended to be higher in children from households with higher wealth ranking than in those from poorer households. Malawi reached lower coverage of the third and fourth doses in clusters with higher malaria prevalence at baseline. Coverage of three doses and of the fourth dose of RTS,S/AS01 tended to be lower among children who did not use an ITN than among ITN users; however, a substantial proportion of non-users of ITNs were reached, with RTS,S/AS01 coverage of three doses among non-users of ITNs ranging from 47% (Kenya) to 74% (Ghana), and for the fourth dose ranging from 23% (Kenya) to 44% (Ghana). Based on these findings, a three-dose schedule would not seem to increase country-level inequities compared to a four-dose schedule.

6.4.3 Modelling exercise

Mathematical modellers explored, in a resource constrained environment, whether reaching more children with three vaccine doses may have greater public health impact and cost effectiveness than reaching fewer children with four doses. For a fixed number of doses and the same delivery cost per dose, the analysis considered various transmission intensities, seasonality settings and coverage level scenarios. Superiority or inferiority of a three-dose or four-dose strategy was considered if there was a greater than 5% decrease or increase in disease burden. The following are the results of this exercise:

- When three-dose and four-dose scenarios are compared across similar transmission settings, modelling estimated that providing more children with a three-dose schedule results in marginal differences (less than 5%) in total disease burden or cost savings compared to vaccinating fewer children with a four-dose schedule.
- However, increased disease burden is sometimes observed when the fourth dose was removed from areas with higher transmission settings to vaccinate additional children in lower transmission settings with a three-dose schedule (who were previously without access to malaria vaccines).

Annex 4 includes more details on the methods and results of this modelling exercise.

6.4.4 Overall assessment of equity

Overall, access to additional malaria prevention through vaccination is expected to increase global health equity, specifically by preventing morbidity and mortality in populations with significant disadvantage. High coverage with malaria vaccines could serve the purpose of reducing inequities in access to malaria control interventions. While a three-dose schedule would seem to achieve this goal by ensuring that more children receive malaria vaccination, the evidence indicates that a four-dose schedule provides substantially greater protection against severe malaria than a three-dose schedule. Mathematical modelling estimated that, within similar transmission levels, providing more children with a three-dose schedule provided similar population health impact as vaccinating fewer children with a four-dose schedule.

From an ethical perspective, maximizing utility is one among many principles for distributing goods, and in the case of malaria vaccines it seems that increasing coverage by reaching more children with three doses compared to reaching fewer children with four doses does not offer greater utility. Consultations with programme managers indicated that changing to or introducing a three-dose schedule may be viewed with distrust by the community as it would be perceived as compromising the level of protection and diluting impact within the population. Equity is not a static concept as populations are complex and dynamic. The goals of equity are best served by clarity of programme aims and continuous monitoring of outcomes to identify whether certain sub-populations are unintentionally excluded or whether disadvantaged groups may be at risk of further marginalization.

7. Modelling of public health impact and cost-effectiveness

The 2019 *Framework for policy decision on RTS,S/AS01 (2)* recommended that cost-effectiveness estimates be regularly refined as data become available in order for the estimates to remain valid and accurate. Cost-effectiveness analyses are informative to WHO, partners and countries. Cost-effectiveness is highly context-specific and estimates could differ considerably depending on country-specific inputs. Nonetheless, cost-effectiveness can be used as one factor to guide decision-making by countries, which should assess affordability and/or cost-effectiveness using locally relevant data. Furthermore, the results of cost-effectiveness analyses are not fixed, and inputs and assumptions may evolve. Notably, the costs of new interventions, including vaccines, are expected to decrease over time, which can markedly impact cost-effectiveness estimates.

Mathematical models were first applied in 2015 to examine the addition of the RTS,S/AS01 malaria vaccine to existing malaria control interventions and treatment, following the conclusion of the Phase 3 trial. These models were developed by multiple groups and used harmonized inputs, drawing on data from the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 clinical trials and malaria disease burden studies. All models predicted a substantial additional public health impact and high cost-effectiveness of RTS,S/AS01 across a wide range of transmission settings (results summarized in Penny et al. (33)). Subsequently, these modelling analyses were updated in 2021 by two of the groups (The Kids Research Institute Australia (The Kids; formerly at Swiss Tropical and Public Health Institute) and Imperial College London (Imperial College)) to estimate impact and cost-effectiveness using data from the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 clinical trials and additional evidence from the MVIP. The models included previously modelled and validated disease and vaccine parameters (from the 2015 analysis), along with assumptions and cost of delivery estimates from the MVIP.

Previous results of public health impact and cost-effectiveness modelling are described in the 2021 *Full evidence report on the RTS,S/AS01 malaria vaccine (3)* and its Annex 9 (34) as well as the 2023 *Full evidence report on the R21/Matrix-M malaria vaccine (18)*.

7.1 Aims and methods

The aims of the modelling exercise in support of the current SAGE and MPAG joint review are two-fold:

- to estimate the public health impact and cost-effectiveness of a three-dose versus four-dose malaria vaccine schedule; and
- to estimate, in the setting of a fixed number of vaccine doses (e.g. due to financial constraints), the public health impact of vaccinating fewer children with a four-dose schedule compared to vaccinating more children with a three-dose schedule (see section 6.4.3).

Modelling estimates are based on the previously used *OpenMalaria* model (The Kids) and the *malariasimulation* model (Imperial College). Detailed methodology and reports by the two groups on the public health impact and cost-effectiveness of a three-dose schedule versus a four-dose schedule are

available in Annex 4. This annex also includes the analyses of allocation scenarios for three-dose and four-dose schedules, which are referred to in section 6.4.

The mathematical modelling by both Imperial College and The Kids followed the same methodology used to estimate impact and cost-effectiveness for RTS,S/AS01 in 2021 and for R21/Matrix-M in 2023; methods have been described elsewhere (3, 18, 34). The public health impact and cost-effectiveness of a three-dose or a four-dose schedule are modelled over a 15-year time horizon across different archetypal settings (representing a range of transmission levels by $PfPR_{2-10}$ and seasonality profiles [either perennial or seasonal], using an age-based vaccination strategy). Results are only presented for the RTS,S/AS01 malaria vaccine, as it is the only vaccine with clinical trial data comparing both three- and four-dose schedules. It is also the vaccine that was introduced through the MVIP and evaluated in the nested case–control study.

Public health impact was estimated for:

- a three-dose RTS,S/AS01 schedule (given at 5, 6 and 7 months of age) relative to no malaria vaccination;
- a four-dose RTS,S/AS01 schedule (first three doses given at 5, 6 and 7 months of age and fourth dose given 12 months after the third dose) relative to no malaria vaccination; and
- a four-dose RTS,S/AS01 schedule relative to a three-dose schedule, enabling an assessment of the incremental impact provided exclusively by the fourth dose.

The costs associated with these comparisons were calculated, including health care costs associated with malaria illness (from a provider perspective), and the costs of the vaccine, related consumables and delivery. These outcomes were used to estimate the incremental cost-effectiveness ratios (ICERs) for several key metrics of malaria burden: uncomplicated malaria cases, malaria deaths and DALYs. The two mathematical models used different case definitions for severe malaria; therefore, the estimated outcomes are not expected to be comparable.

The median incremental cost per DALY averted of four doses compared to three doses was assessed against tiered cost-effectiveness thresholds, according to interim WHO methodology (52),¹¹ based on gross domestic product (GDP) per capita. Interventions with an ICER less than half of a country's GDP per capita ($< 0.5 \times \text{GDP per capita}$) are considered to be highly cost-effective; ICERs that are $0.5\text{--}1.0 \times \text{GDP}$ are considered to be moderately cost-effective; and ICERs exceeding $1 \times \text{GDP}$ per capita are considered to be lower priority (unless justified by other factors, e.g. urgency, equity or lack of alternatives). For the malaria vaccine mathematical modelling results in this report, the 2024 per capita GDPs for 42 malaria-endemic countries in sub-Saharan Africa were used to determine country-specific cost-effectiveness thresholds.

The dose schedules used in the modelled estimates include a three-dose schedule (given at 5, 6, and 7 months of age) and a four-dose schedule (with the first three doses given at 5, 6, and 7 months of age, and the fourth dose given 12 months after the third dose). Children are vaccinated as they become age-eligible, beginning at a fixed time point and continuing throughout the evaluation period; outcomes are monitored in all age groups over the 15 years following vaccine introduction. Several coverage scenarios of the first three doses and fourth dose are considered through sensitivity analysis. Key model inputs and assumptions are provided in Table 6.

¹¹ WHO has recently used an interim guidance for prioritizing HIV, viral hepatitis and STI interventions based on tiered cost-effectiveness thresholds. This approach was designed to support urgent decision-making in resource-constrained settings and is interim guidance, pending formal WHO guidance on cost-effectiveness thresholds.

Table 6. Model inputs and assumptions for public health impact and cost-effectiveness analysis (see Annex 4 for modelling details and sources)

Model input	Assumption
Transmission intensity	<i>PfPR</i> ₂₋₁₀ between 3% and 45%
Seasonality	One seasonal and one perennial archetype
Case management	45% probability of access to treatment for uncomplicated malaria ^a 48% probability of access to hospital care for severe malaria (Kids model). Imperial College London models hospitalized severe cases only.
Other interventions	Non-vaccine malaria interventions already in place are assumed to contribute to the current baseline level of transmission and no additional non-vaccine interventions (above those already in place at the start of vaccination) are explicitly modelled.
Vaccination delivery approach and schedules	Age-based with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • three-dose schedule: 5, 6 and 7 months of age • four-dose schedule: 5, 6, 7 and 19 months of age (fourth dose given 12 months after third dose)
Vaccine price ^b (including consumables)	US\$ 6.50 per dose (US\$ 5.00 per dose ^c + US\$ 1.50 consumables costs)
Cost of delivery estimate ^b	US\$ 1.56 per dose
Cost of malaria case management ^b	Age- and severity- specific cost of treatment (see Annex 4)

^a The Kids model varies access to treatment for uncomplicated malaria (normally distributed about the stated values, using a standard deviation of 10).

^b All costs are in 2025 US\$, with the cost-effectiveness analysis including 3% annual discounting for both costs and outcomes. Cost-effectiveness is assessed from a provider perspective.

^c While US\$ 5 per dose does not reflect current prices for RTS,S/AS01 (see section 6.1.1), it is reflective of GSK and Bharat Biotech's announcement that the price of the RTS,S/AS01 vaccine would be reduced by more than half, progressively, to less than US\$ 5 per dose by 2028 (40).

7.2 Model validation to RTS,S/AS01 case–control study data

To consider the comparative impact of a three-dose schedule and a four-dose schedule, models were validated and calibrated to data available from the RTS,S/AS01 case–control study, as well as to results from the RTS,S/AS01 MVIP evaluations during 46 months of surveillance.

Both models were assessed for alignment with vaccine effectiveness against severe malaria from the RTS,S/AS01 case–control analysis (conducted in the MVIP evaluation's vaccine implementing areas of Ghana, Kenya and Malawi).

The models were calibrated to each MVIP country using malaria population prevalence data from children 5–48 months of age, collected during the MVIP cross-sectional endline household surveys. This calibration enabled estimation of the country-specific entomological inoculation rate, reflective of local transmission intensity in the vaccination clusters. The models also accounted for seasonality, treatment coverage, ITN use (each informed by Malaria Atlas Project estimates), and survey timing. Vaccination delivery was modelled to replicate the 2019 malaria vaccination schedules in Ghana, Kenya and Malawi (third dose at

9 months of age [Ghana, Kenya] or 7 months of age [Malawi], and fourth dose at 24 months of age [Ghana, Kenya] or 22 months of age [Malawi]).

Both models were validated against data on vaccine effectiveness against severe malaria from the MVIP case–control study. For the Imperial College model, calibrated to the Phase 3 RTS,S vaccine trial, vaccine model parameters were recalibrated to obtain an improved fit to the case–control study data, resulting in a model-estimated median incremental effectiveness of 19–22% for four doses compared to three doses. The Kids model largely captured the effectiveness found in the MVIP case–control study and was therefore not recalibrated; for the period up to 12 months after the fourth dose, the modelled effect of the fourth dose is possibly lower than vaccine effectiveness against severe malaria observed from the MVIP case control study data.

More detailed explanations of the model validation and fits are available in Annex 4.

7.3 Results

7.3.1 Modelled public health impact

Estimates from both models indicate that, compared to a three-dose schedule, the four-dose RTS,S/AS01 vaccine schedule always has a higher impact on uncomplicated malaria cases, malaria deaths and DALYs averted across malaria transmission levels and seasonal settings. The absolute reduction in cases increases with transmission intensity, although the impact on deaths is estimated to plateau at moderate transmission settings. The Imperial College model estimated that the fourth dose has a 31% additional impact on malaria cases at 20% $PfPR_{2-10}$ (range across simulations in 3–45% $PfPR_{2-10}$ is 25–33%) and a 34% (range 17–40%) additional impact on deaths. At a $PfPR_{2-10}$ of 20%, the Kids model estimated that the fourth dose provides a 28% additional reduction in cases (19–42% range across transmission settings) and a 26% (8–48%) additional reduction in deaths.

More detailed results from Imperial College and The Kids are available in Annex 4.

Fig. 15. Estimated uncomplicated malaria cases, malaria deaths and DALYs averted in all ages per 100 000 population by vaccination with three or four doses, compared to no vaccination, over 15 years, by transmission intensity and seasonal settings RTS(A: Imperial College; B: OpenMalaria, The Kids). Simulations assumed 80% coverage of the first three doses and 20% drop-off for the fourth dose.

7.3.2 Cost-effectiveness

The three-dose and a four-dose schedules were found to have a similar range of cost per DALY averted compared to no vaccination. For the Imperial model, at a cost of US\$ 5 per dose of RTS,S/AS01 and in settings with 10–45% $PfPR_{2-10}$, the median incremental cost per DALY averted was very similar for the three-dose and four-dose schedule, ranging from US\$ 132 to US\$ 231 for three doses, compared to zero doses, and from US\$ 128 to US\$ 224 for four doses, compared to zero doses (Fig. 16A). For the Kids model, at the same cost per dose and across settings with 10–45% $PfPR_{2-10}$, the median incremental cost per DALY averted ranged from US\$ 139 to US\$ 256 for three doses, compared to zero doses, and from US\$ 144 to US\$ 262 for four doses, compared to zero doses.

Fig. 16. Median ICERs for three doses (orange) or four doses (yellow) of RTS,S/AS01 compared to no vaccination for A) Imperial College model and B) OpenMalaria model, The Kids, indicating estimated incremental cost per DALY averted in 2025 US\$, by transmission intensity

The Imperial College model found that the median incremental cost per DALY averted of four doses compared to three doses ranged from US\$ 99 to US\$ 159 in settings with 10–45% $PfPR_{2-10}$ (Fig. 17A). The incremental cost per case averted of four doses compared to three doses ranged from US\$ 19 to US\$ 49. For the Kids model, the median incremental cost per DALY averted of four doses compared to three doses ranged from US\$ 166 to US\$ 214 in settings with 10–45% $PfPR_{2-10}$ (Fig. 17B). In the same settings, the incremental cost per case averted of four doses compared to three doses ranged from US\$ 18 to US\$ 73.

In malaria-endemic countries in sub-Saharan Africa,¹² the fourth dose was considered highly cost-effective ($< 0.5 \times$ GDP per capita) in all four upper middle-income countries, all 19 lower middle-income countries, and 18 of 19 low-income countries. In one of the 19 low-income countries, the fourth dose was considered moderately cost-effective for a $PfPR_{2-10} > 10\%$.

Fig. 17. ICERs for four doses compared to three doses of RTS,S by transmission intensity, indicating estimated incremental cost per DALY averted, in 2025 US\$ for A) Imperial College model and B) OpenMalaria model, The Kids.

More detailed results from Imperial College and The Kids are available in Annex 4.

¹² A total of 42 countries with available data on 2024 GDP per capita

7.4 Conclusions on modelled public health impact and cost-effectiveness of a four-dose versus three-dose RTS,S/AS01 malaria vaccination schedule

Mathematical modelling by two independent research groups estimated that the fourth dose of RTS,S/AS01 provides additional impact over a three-dose schedule. This is consistent with the data observed in the RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial and the MVIP case-control study.

Overall, both a three-dose and a four-dose schedule of RTS,S/AS01 malaria vaccine were found to have positive public health impact in terms of uncomplicated malaria cases, malaria deaths and DALYs averted. Both schedules were found to be highly cost-effective in moderate and high transmission settings for nearly all malaria-endemic countries in sub-Saharan Africa.

Modelling estimates of the public health impact and cost-effectiveness of a three-dose R21/Matrix-M schedule were not included because there are no empirical data on the efficacy or effectiveness of a three-dose schedule of R21/Matrix-M. Previous estimates of the cost-effectiveness of a four-dose R21/Matrix-M schedule show that it is also highly cost-effective and comparable with other malaria interventions and other childhood vaccines, noting that the results are highly context-specific and can vary depending on the assumed levels of prevention and treatment measures already in place at the time of vaccine introduction.

8. Working Group conclusions and recommendations for SAGE/MPAG consideration

8.1 Assessment of efficacy and effectiveness

Information from all available research and programme evaluations provides strong evidence that a four-dose vaccine schedule for RTS,S/AS01 is superior to a three-dose schedule in preventing clinical and severe malaria.

The RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial showed that a four-dose vaccine schedule provided efficacy and impact against clinical and severe malaria in children vaccinated from 5 months of age. Although a three-dose schedule was efficacious against clinical malaria, the fourth dose provided an incremental efficacy against clinical malaria of 26% and a longer duration of protection. Furthermore, among children randomized to the three-dose schedule, waning efficacy resulted in a loss of protection against severe malaria, suggesting a potential rebound effect (a period of excess malaria after time-limited protection). The findings suggested that a fourth dose may be required to maintain efficacy against severe malaria. Subsequent review of the clinical trial data showed a lower vaccine efficacy against severe malaria in the three-dose group compared to the four-dose group before the administration of the fourth dose; this divergence brought into question the interpretation of the comparison of the findings between the group that had received the fourth dose and the group that had not. An extended follow-up study at three of the Phase 3 trial sites indicated that the benefit against clinical or severe malaria was retained among children who received three or four vaccine doses, noting that the point estimates for vaccine efficacy against both clinical and severe malaria were higher in the four-dose group than in the three-dose group. Importantly, there was no excess in cases of severe malaria (rebound) in any group during seven years of follow-up, suggesting that any rebound that may have occurred was time-limited.

The RTS,S/AS01 cluster-randomized pilot implementation (MVIP) demonstrated an impact on severe malaria and all-cause mortality, despite low uptake of the fourth dose. There was no evidence of rebound severe malaria in the magnitude observed during the Phase 3 trial.

The RTS,S/AS01 case–control study nested within the MVIP was designed specifically to assess the value of the fourth dose, the incremental benefit of four doses over three doses, and the occurrence of rebound of severe malaria cases if a child were to receive only three doses of RTS,S/AS01. If the recently completed case–control study showed that a fourth dose provides minimal incremental impact over a safe and effective three-dose schedule, there could be some contexts in which three doses could be recommended as an alternative to four doses. Results from the case–control study showed the following:

- Compared to the protection from three doses, the fourth dose provided an incremental effectiveness against severe malaria of **30%** (95% CI: 9–45%).
- A three-dose RTS,S/AS01 schedule is safe and effective against severe malaria, including cerebral malaria. Receipt of three vaccine doses provided better protection against clinical and severe malaria than no vaccination. Before the scheduled age when the fourth dose was due, receipt of three doses of RTS,S/AS01 was associated with **56%** (95% CI: 40–67%) protection against severe malaria.
- For children who received the fourth dose, the protection was sustained at least 18 months after receipt of the fourth dose – with cumulative protection of **54%** (95% CI: 39–66%). If children missed the fourth dose, there was evidence of continued – albeit reduced – protection (**35%**; 95% CI: 15–50%).
- Effects are broadly consistent with the vaccine efficacy against clinical malaria measured in the

RTS,S/AS01 Phase 3 trial in the sites with low and moderate transmission, as well as the impact observed against severe malaria in the cluster-randomized MVIP evaluations.

8.2 Assessment of safety

Both recommended vaccines (RTS,S/AS01 and R21/Matrix-M) have a good safety profile. In the RTS,S/AS01 case-control study, there was no rebound effect observed in children who received three vaccine doses; in contrast, children had sustained protection.

8.3 Assessment of resource use, impact and cost-effectiveness

A three-dose schedule would be less costly to procure and deliver than a four-dose schedule (by about 25%). However, the actual savings are likely to be lower and will vary depending on drop-out rates and country context. The reduced vaccination programme costs should be weighed against suboptimal protection (30% incremental effectiveness against severe malaria provided by the fourth dose) and the increased costs associated with a rise in cases of clinical and severe malaria.

Modelling estimated that a four-dose RTS,S/AS01 schedule always has a higher impact than a three-dose schedule in terms of uncomplicated malaria cases, malaria deaths and DALYs averted, across a range of malaria transmission levels and seasonal settings. The three-dose and four-dose schedules were found to have a similar range of cost per DALY averted compared to no RTS,S/AS01 vaccination. Both a three-dose schedule and four-dose schedule were found to be highly cost-effective in moderate and high transmission settings for nearly all malaria-endemic countries in sub-Saharan Africa, which is generally consistent with previous analyses.

8.4 Assessment of feasibility and acceptability

Both a three-dose schedule and four-dose schedule were assessed as feasible to deliver. Completing a three-dose schedule within the first year of life would be more achievable for individual children than completing a four-dose schedule that extends into the second or third year of life; however, most countries provide routine childhood vaccinations and health services in the second year of life – with which the fourth dose could be aligned – and efforts are ongoing to improve uptake at those visits.

Consulted ministry of health officials stated that a four-dose schedule that clearly provides higher protection is more acceptable and preferable for both the ministries of health and target population over a schedule that results in lower protection (three-dose schedule). Consulted ministry of health officials cautioned that national immunization programmes and ministries of health risk losing credibility and public confidence if they change from a four-dose schedule to a less effective three-dose schedule after health workers and caregivers have been informed that four doses are needed for the best protection (as shown by the data).

8.5 Assessment of equity

Overall, access to additional malaria prevention through vaccination is expected to increase global health equity, specifically by preventing morbidity and mortality in populations with significant disadvantage. While a three-dose schedule would seem to achieve this goal by ensuring that more children receive malaria vaccination, the evidence indicates that a four-dose schedule provides substantially greater protection against severe malaria than a three-dose schedule. Mathematical modelling estimates that, within similar transmission levels and a fixed number of vaccine doses, providing more children with a three-dose schedule provided similar population health impact as vaccinating fewer children with a four-dose schedule.

From an ethical perspective, maximizing utility is one among many principles for distributing goods, and

in the case of malaria vaccines it seems that increasing coverage by reaching more children with three doses compared to reaching fewer children with four doses does not offer greater utility. Consultations with programme managers indicated that changing to or introducing a three-dose schedule may be viewed with distrust by the community as it would be perceived as compromising the level of protection and diluting impact within the population.

8.6 Working Group recommendations

A four-dose schedule provides higher protection against clinical and severe malaria than a three-dose schedule and should remain the recommendation for use. The incremental effectiveness of the fourth dose against severe malaria is substantial. Although the delivery of a three-dose schedule would be simpler and less costly, these factors do not outweigh the substantial clinical benefit provided by a fourth dose. WHO recommends that countries align the timing of the fourth vaccine dose with the timing of other vaccines administered in the second year of life, thereby reducing the additional delivery burden.

Previous WHO recommendations to reduce the number of vaccine doses for other vaccines (e.g. PCV, HPV vaccine) have been based on data indicating that fewer vaccine doses would provide similar effectiveness to that of the originally recommended number of doses. This is not the case for RTS,S/AS01, as evidence from the Phase 3 trial showed a 26% incremental effectiveness of the four-dose schedule above that provided by the three-dose schedule in reducing clinical malaria, and evidence from the MVIP case-control study showed a 30% incremental effectiveness of the four-dose schedule above three doses in reducing severe malaria.

Evidence demonstrates that the first three doses provide protection in areas of perennial malaria transmission and are safe, with continued protection if a fourth dose is missed. However, protection against severe malaria is substantially higher with four doses than with three doses.

Children living in areas of conflict or where the delivery of second-year-of-life vaccines is not operationally feasible can benefit from a three-dose schedule until obstacles to the delivery of a fourth dose are resolved.

Although there are no data comparing a three-dose schedule to a four-dose schedule for R21/Matrix-M, because of the similarity of the vaccine construct to RTS,S/AS01, the Working Group considers conclusions based on RTS,S/AS01 evidence as applicable to both vaccines.

Given the continued threat of malaria to young children as a leading cause of childhood death in Africa, and given the recent reduction in global financial support for malaria control, the malaria vaccine manufacturers are strongly encouraged to reduce vaccine prices, and Gavi is encouraged to advance market-shaping activities so that children at risk can benefit from the best vaccine schedule.

8.6.1 Implementation considerations

Please refer to the May 2024 WHO position paper on malaria vaccines (1).

8.6.2 Monitoring and evaluation

- Noting that equity is not a static concept as populations are complex and dynamic, monitor the implementation of the malaria vaccines programme to ensure that sub-populations are not unfairly excluded or that populations experiencing disadvantage are not further disadvantaged as malaria vaccines are rolled out.

Please refer to the May 2024 WHO position paper on malaria vaccines (1).

8.6.3 Research recommendations

- Assess vaccine efficacy, duration of protection and cost-effectiveness of a three-dose R21/Matrix-M schedule (with no fourth dose).
- Conduct clinical studies of fractional doses to determine whether smaller doses of vaccine could be equally efficacious.

Please also refer to the May 2024 WHO position paper on malaria vaccines (1).

9. List of annexes

Annex 1: Evidence-to-recommendation table of 3-dose versus 4-dose malaria vaccination schedule in perennial areas

Annex 2: GRADE tables of 3-dose versus 4-dose malaria vaccination schedule in perennial areas

Annex 3: RTS,S/AS01 case–control study analysis report

Annex 4: Modelled public health impact and cost-effectiveness of 3-dose versus 4-dose malaria vaccination schedule in perennial areas

10. SAGE/MPAG Working Group on Malaria Vaccines membership and Terms of Reference

As of 1 September 2025, members of the SAGE/MPAG Working Group on Malaria Vaccines include:

- Nick Andrews
- Kwando Odei Antwi-Agyei
- Graham Brown**
- Patrick Kachur
- Corine Karema
- Kim Mulholland*
- Eusebio Macete (Co-Chair)
- Kathleen Neuzil*
- Faith Osier
- Regina Rabinovich
- Esperança Sevens
- Laurence Slutsker
- Peter Smith (Chair)

*SAGE members

**MPAG members

Terms of Reference are accessible here: <https://www.who.int/initiatives/malaria-vaccine-implementation-programme/sage-mpag-working-group>.

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